

Online Appendix

Marcel Rojahn^{a,*} and Marcus Grum^a

^aUniversity of Potsdam, Junior Chair of Business Information Systems, esp. AI-based Application Systems, Karl-Marx-Str. 67, Potsdam, 14469, Brandenburg, Germany

This online appendix accompanies the paper:

“Green Artificial Intelligence and Its Lifecycle, Hardware, and Measurement Dimensions”

An earlier version of this online appendix was made available together with the preprint version of the manuscript at arXiv:2511.07090. The present version has been revised to accompany the accepted manuscript version of the article in Information and Software Technology Rojahn and Grum (2026) .

*Corresponding author. ORCID: 0000-0002-2231-5690

Email address: marcel.rojahn@uni-potsdam.de (Marcel Rojahn)

Introduction and structure of the online appendix

This online appendix documents supplementary materials on the review procedure, data extraction, and the synthesis of results.

Section Appendix A provides the transparency materials for the review procedure and data extraction, covering the review workflow, database coverage and search strings, eligibility criteria, screening and deduplication procedures, inter-rater agreement reporting, and the extraction, appraisal, and synthesis methods.

Section Appendix B reports the descriptive characteristics of the analyzed corpus, including publication dynamics, publication outlets, and document types.

Section Appendix C reports the detailed literature analysis, including the distribution of articles across the Green AI concept areas, the consolidation of definitions and lifecycle-related terminology, and the analytical steps from term-level evidence to the synthesized lifecycle structure.

Section Appendix D: synthesis of Green AI lifecycle phases and sub-phases.

Section Appendix E: illustrative view of the synthesized categories.

Section Appendix F: descriptive summaries of the extracted results.

Section Appendix G outlines the linkage between the synthesized lifecycle structure and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) stages.

Section Appendix H provides additional transparency-oriented views of the synthesized results.

Section Appendix I summarizes supplementary material on hardware aspects.

Section Appendix J provides supplementary material on measurement approaches and their comparison.

Appendix A. Transparency materials on review procedure and data extraction

Appendix A.1. Review procedure overview

Figure A.1 summarizes the review workflow adapted from Thomé et al (2016); the following sections detail database coverage and search strings (Phase 1), eligibility criteria (Phase 2), screening and de-duplication procedures with cross-checking of screening and coding decisions (Phase 3), and extraction, appraisal, and synthesis methods (Phase 4). To support transparency and consistency, the review procedure was specified in advance, and key screening or coding decisions were cross-checked.

Figure A.1: Eight-step process used in this systematic literature review (SLR) (adapted from (Thomé et al., 2016)).

Appendix A.2. Databases and search strings

Primary databases were *Web of Science* (Topic: Title, Abstract, Author Keywords, Keywords Plus), *ScienceDirect* (Title, Abstract, Author Keywords), and *IEEE Xplore* (journals and conferences). To capture leading AI venues not consistently indexed—specifically NeurIPS, ICML, and ICLR—*arXiv* was queried; preprints were flagged and handled as specified in Phase 2. Field-restricted Boolean search strings were iteratively refined across three concept groups: (i) domain and context (industry, manufacturing, production, automation); (ii) impact dimensions (emissions/carbon, CO₂, power/energy, efficiency/performance); and (iii) AI scope (AI, machine learning, deep learning) (Figure A.2). During screening, lifecycle/measurement terminology (e.g., LCA; Scope 3/embodied impacts; Water Usage Effectiveness, WUE; Power Usage Effectiveness, PUE; dynamic voltage and frequency scaling, DVFS; running average power limit, RAPL; direct power metering; estimator calibration; location- versus market-based emission factors; carbon-aware scheduling; edge-cloud placement; uncertainty disclosure) was used for backward and forward citation chaining to capture articles on water, value-chain impacts, and calibration/uncertainty well beyond purely energy- and carbon-centric work. This targeted chaining was documented in the protocol and did not alter selection decisions; instead, it served to verify

documented coverage across impact dimensions and to enable critical cross-checks between provider dashboards and metering-based articles.

Figure A.2: Core keyword groups and terms used for the database searches (domain/context, impact dimensions, AI scope).

Appendix A.3. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Consistent with standards for systematic reviews (Light and Pillemer, 1984; Durach et al., 2017), the primary evidence base was restricted to (i) peer-reviewed journal articles (retrieved via *Web of Science*, *ScienceDirect*, *IEEE Xplore*), (ii) peer-reviewed conference proceedings indexed in *IEEE Xplore* or *ACM Digital Library*, as well as proceedings series accessible via *ScienceDirect* where paper-level peer review was indicated in the record, (iii) peer-reviewed book chapters in edited volumes with documented external review, and (iv) scholarly monographs from academic presses with documented external peer review and an explicit methods section on energy/measurement or LCA. Preprints, provider dashboards, tool repositories, and web resources were retained only for mapping, citation chaining, tool documentation, or contextual transparency, and were not treated as primary evidence unless explicitly stated. Where a journal version existed, it superseded the preprint.

In addition to outlet-level peer review, *methodological eligibility* required an AI focus and at least one of the following: (a) quantitative reporting of energy/power or compute intensity, or of carbon/water/embodied impacts; (b) lifecycle boundary specification or mapping to LCA stages; or (c) explicit measurement/telemetry or calibration procedures (e.g., RAPL; direct power metering; emission factor specification).

Exclusions covered grey literature (e.g., theses, white papers, blogs), non-English texts (for terminology consistency and database coverage), and articles before 2014 (onset of the modern deep-learning era and associated measurement/efficiency literature). Eligibility criteria were explicitly aligned

with the research questions (RQ1-RQ5) and the taxonomy-based scope description (Table A.1), thereby minimizing scope drift and selection bias. Review articles were retained for mapping and citation chaining but not treated as primary evidence unless they introduced standardized measurement assets (e.g., emission factor models with documented provenance, metering calibration protocols, or LCA boundary definitions) or unique, otherwise unavailable benchmark datasets.

Appendix A.4. Screening and de-duplication

The literature search commenced in October 2024, with final data extraction completed in August 2025. The PRISMA flow (Figure A.3) documents records identified through database searching—*Web of Science* (1,035), *ScienceDirect* (318), and *IEEE Xplore* (326)—for a total of 1,679 items, plus 16 records from other sources (e.g., provider dashboards and tool repositories), yielding 1,695 items before documented eligibility screening and de-duplication procedures.

After automated de-duplication that first collapsed records by digital object identifier (DOI) and otherwise by normalized title-first-author-year tuples (case-folded; diacritics and punctuation removed; fuzzy title matching using a documented token-set ratio threshold), and after applying documented filters (English language; year ≥ 2014 ; document type: journal or conference; preprints permitted and flagged; journal versions superseding preprints), 757 records remained for title/abstract screening by two independent assessors. In line with Thomé et al 2016, titles, keywords, and abstracts were independently assessed against predefined inclusion/exclusion criteria and the research questions, thereby narrowing the dataset from 757 to 98 articles for full-text assessment. Of the 757 records screened, 659 were excluded at this stage.

At the full-text stage, 2 articles were excluded because they lacked sufficient Green AI relevance or methodological transparency in measurement and reporting, leaving 96 database-sourced articles. Backward and forward citation chaining then added 7 articles, resulting in a final total of 103 included articles.

Appendix A.5. Information extraction schema

A structured extraction schema captured: bibliographic data; lifecycle phases and mapping to LCA stages; impact dimensions (energy, carbon, water, embodied/material); measurement approach (estimator versus direct

Figure A.3: PRISMA 2020 flow diagram of article selection (Oct 2024-Aug 2025) (Adapted from (Page et al., 2021)).

metering; device- versus facility-level); hardware and deployment context (central processing units, CPU; graphics processing units, GPUs; domain-specific tensor/neural processing units, TPUs/NPUs; edge-cloud placement; region/ energy mix; cooling); algorithmic/system levers (compression, DVFS, power capping, carbon-aware scheduling); reporting completeness (International System of Units, emission factor provenance, reproducibility artifacts); and auxiliary elements such as provider-specific dashboards and end-of-life treatment of hardware. Beyond these categories, the schema enforced traceability between lifecycle stages and reported indicators, with independent cross-checking of selected coding decisions supporting consistency and reducing subjective bias. Linkage fields mapped AI tasks to standardized LCA stages, and detailed measurement provenance (e.g., market- versus location-based carbon factors, water withdrawal versus actual consumption) was explicitly captured.

Appendix A.6. Descriptive orientation of the review scope

The following descriptors based on established review taxonomies are included only to document the general orientation of the review. They should not be read as an additional methodological contribution beyond the review procedure summarized in the main manuscript.

The review scope is structured using the framework by vom Brocke et

al. (2009) and Cooper’s taxonomy (1988) (Table A.1). Specifically: (1) Focus—research outcomes, research methods, and theories; (2) Goal—integration across environmental assessment, lifecycle coverage mapped to LCA stages, and benchmarking of reporting practices; (3) Perspective—neutral representation, avoiding bias across methodological and epistemic stances; (4) Coverage—representative across computer science, environmental science, and engineering, with targeted inclusion of top-tier AI venues (e.g., NeurIPS, ICML, ICLR via proceedings indices, with arXiv preprints flagged accordingly) and domain journals (e.g., *Communications of the ACM*, *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, *Journal of Cleaner Production*); (5) Organization—conceptual and lifecycle-explicit, along the Green AI lifecycle with impact metrics (energy in J or kWh; carbon footprint in kg CO₂e; water use; embodied/material impacts) and (6) Audience—general scholars, practitioners, and policymakers.

Table A.1: Review scope characterized using established taxonomy dimensions. Bold entries denote applied categories.

Legend: - Characteristic Regular - Category Bold - Applied category				
1. Focus	Research outcomes	Research methods	Theories	Practices or applications
2. Goal	Integration		Criticism	Identification of central issues
3. Perspective	Neutral representation		Espousal of position	
4. Coverage	Exhaustive	Exhaustive with selective citation	Representative	Central or pivotal
5. Organization	Historical	Conceptual		Methodological
6. Audience	Specialized scholars	General scholars	Practitioners or policy makers	General public

The literature search proceeded in four phases: (1) identifying databases and iteratively refining field-restricted search strings; (2) specifying transparent inclusion and exclusion criteria; (3) executing the queries and screening titles/abstracts and full texts (PRISMA in Figure A.3); and (4) consolidating the final article set and preparing the structured extraction corpus.

Appendix B. Article corpus characteristics

Figure B.4a shows a sustained rise in Green AI articles that are explicitly energy- and measurement-focused since 2019. Based on the curated corpus (cut-off date: 7 Aug 2025), yearly counts are 6 (2019), 8 (2020), 15 (2021),

14 (2022), 22 (2023), 24 (2024), and 4 (2025), for a total of 91 items over 2019-2025. This trajectory closely coincides with rapidly growing attention to AI’s environmental footprint in the literature (Strubell et al., 2019).

To distinguish consistently active venues from sporadic contributors, Figure B.4b displays outlets with at least two peer-reviewed articles in 2019–2025: *Communications of the ACM* (4), *Journal of Machine Learning Research* (3), *IEEE Access* (2), *Sustainability* (2), and *Applied Sciences* (2). Within the broader documented source set used for mapping, tool documentation, and contextual transparency, journals account for 40 items (43.0%), conference papers for 21 (22.6%), preprints for 14 (15.1%), web resources for 10 (10.8%), books for 3 (3.2%), book chapters for 2 (2.2%), and other types for 1 (1.1%). Item types follow `journalArticle`, `conferencePaper`, `preprint`, `webpage`, `book`, `bookSection`, and `document`. For the outlets figure, only peer-reviewed journals and established conferences are included (preprints and web resources excluded).

(a) Annual and cumulative Green AI articles (2019–2025).

(b) Number of articles per outlet (journals and conferences only).

Figure B.4: Comparison of Green AI article trends, 2019-2025.

Appendix C. Literature analysis

Figure C.5: Distribution of articles across Green AI concepts (multi-label; base $n = 103$).

Appendix C.1. Definition-related source overview

Table C.2 consolidates explicit Green AI definitions and definition-related formulations used in the literature. The left column lists the sources. The excerpts in the middle column are reproduced verbatim for definitional comparison and are attributed to the corresponding sources in the left column. The right column summarizes source-specific analytical limitations relevant to conceptual delimitation and operationalization.

Table C.2: Explicit Green AI definitions and definition-related assessment formulations in the literature, with their relevance for the synthesized definition and source-specific analytical limitations.

Source	Verbatim definition-related excerpt	Relevance for synthesized definition and analytical limitations
(Schwartz et al., 2020)	The term Green AI refers to AI research that yields novel results while taking into account the computational cost, encouraging a reduction in resources spent.	Efficiency-centric definition focused on computational cost reduction. It supports the performance–cost logic of the synthesized definition, but does not specify lifecycle-wide environmental accounting, embodied impacts, water use, or formal system boundaries. Later reporting metrics include work, FPO, electricity use, and carbon emissions, but not a full lifecycle impact-accounting framework.
(Xu et al., 2021)	Green AI, appeals to researchers to obtain novel results without increasing computational cost rather, ideally reducing it.	Efficiency-centric definition focused on reducing computational cost while maintaining novel or competitive results. The survey discusses training- and inference-related indicators such as FLOPs, runtime, carbon emissions, and model size but does not define lifecycle-wide boundaries, embodied impacts, water use, or broader environmental accounting criteria.
(Patterson et al., 2022)	Green AI where the focus is on computing efficiency as well as model quality.	Characterization focused on computing efficiency and model quality rather than a fully specified Green AI definition. The paper addresses operational energy, carbon accounting, data center efficiency such as PUE, and location-dependent carbon intensity. Its main analytical focus remains on operational training-related emissions and best practices. Embodied and full lifecycle impacts are acknowledged but are not treated as the central assessment scope.
(Ligozat et al., 2022)	The goal of a life cycle assessment consists in computing the sum of the environmental flows of the system associated with a functional unit.	Definition-related assessment formulation rather than an explicit Green AI definition. It provides a basis for lifecycle-based environmental accounting through system definition, environmental flows, and functional-unit-based comparability. This is relevant for the boundary and reference-condition logic of the synthesized definition. However, the formulation does not define Green AI itself and does not specify functional performance as a Green AI criterion.
(Chen et al., 2023)	The research efforts of Green AI also reveal the critical need to take environmental impacts into major consideration when developing AI.	Green AI is framed as an efficiency-oriented response to Red AI and as a call to consider environmental impacts in AI development. The paper embeds Green AI within sustainable AI, but does not provide an operational Green AI definition with lifecycle boundaries, hardware/infrastructure scope, or concrete environmental accounting criteria.
(Martínez-Fernández et al., 2023)	Approaches to build AI models that are environmentally friendly and inclusive.	High-level project-oriented characterization of Green AI as environmentally friendly and inclusive AI model building. It does not specify measurable environmental indicators, system boundaries, or lifecycle scope. By combining environmental friendliness with inclusiveness, the specifically environmental content remains comparatively underdetermined.
(Tornede et al., 2023)	Advocating to consider the energy efficiency of AI algorithms during their development.	Green AI is used as the basis for Green AutoML and remains centered on energy efficiency, benchmarking, runtime, carbon emissions, and transparency. The formulation supports performance–budget reasoning, but does not provide a general Green AI definition with lifecycle boundaries, embodied impacts, or a full environmental accounting framework.
(Verdecchia et al., 2023)	Green AI regards practices aimed at utilizing AI to mitigate the impact that humans have on the natural environment in terms of natural resources utilized or mitigating the impact that AI itself can have on the natural environment.	Broad review-derived definition covering both AI for environmental mitigation and mitigation of AI’s own environmental impact. It accommodates energy, carbon, and wider footprint perspectives, but does not sharply separate Green AI from adjacent AI-for-sustainability strands or provide concrete operational measurement criteria within the definition itself.
(Clemm et al., 2024)	We propose a life-cycle-based system thinking approach that accounts for the four key elements of these software-hardware-systems: model, data, server, and cloud.	Assessment-oriented formulation rather than a standalone Green AI definition. It is relevant for the system-level and lifecycle-boundary logic of the synthesized definition because it links Green AI assessment to model, data, server, and cloud. Functional performance is addressed elsewhere through the aim of reducing computation while preserving accurate results, but it is not specified here as a formal definitional condition. A complete multi-impact protocol and explicit reference conditions are not provided.
(Alzoubi and Mishra, 2024)	The application of AI technology with an emphasis on energy consumption, CO ₂ e reduction, and environmental sustainability.	Broad review-based framing that combines energy consumption, CO ₂ e reduction, sustainable model design, measurement and optimization tools, regulation, and “green-by AI” applications. The concept is used broadly and is not narrowed into an operational definition with explicit assessment boundaries, reference conditions, or lifecycle-wide criteria.
(Bolón-Canedo et al., 2024)	A new paradigm, called Green AI, which incorporates sustainable practices and techniques in model design, training, and deployment that aim to reduce the associated environmental cost and carbon footprint.	Broad paradigm-oriented framing covering model design, training, deployment, energy and water consumption, measurement tools, regulation, and green-in/green-by AI. It is relevant for lifecycle and multi-impact awareness, but it does not provide a narrowly delimited operational definition with explicit system boundaries and reference conditions.

Appendix D. Synthesis of Green AI lifecycle phases

Appendix D.1. State-of-the-art of Green AI lifecycle stages

To quantify how Green AI is distributed across the AI lifecycle, the analysis moves from term-level evidence to phase-level evidence in six bounded steps. Step 1 produces a harmonized vocabulary from the 43-article corpus (164 lifecycle-related term groups via keyword-in-context extraction and synonym consolidation (Frantzi et al., 2000)). Step 2 computes length-normalized frequencies and a composite salience score to separate head from tail. Step 3 builds a chronological heatmap for the 34 highest-salience terms. Step 4 derives a dendrogram from term co-occurrence to fix a stable, semantically consistent column order. Step 5 aggregates terms into phases/subphases. Finally, step 6 can quantify coverage (criterion prevalence, mean per phase, overall breadth) (Egghe and Rousseau, 2008; Donthu et al., 2021). This procedure can be used to explore patterns of over- and under-representation across lifecycle areas.

Step 1—Identification and grouping of lifecycle-related terms.

From the 43 articles in the SLR, keyword-in-context analysis of titles, abstracts, and author keywords extracted 164 lifecycle-relevant terms. Frequency thresholds removed singletons, and consolidation of morphological variants (e.g., “train” versus “training”) and technical synonyms (e.g., “deployment” versus “operationalization”) produced the harmonized set: (e.g., *training*; *model training*; *deployment*; *operationalization*) (Frantzi et al., 2000). The candidate set was generated from both author-provided keywords and automated term extraction from titles and abstracts, ensuring documented representation of domain-specific vocabulary across all AI lifecycle stages.

To maximize conceptual precision and eliminate redundancy, synonymous or closely related expressions were consolidated into unified term clusters (e.g., *training*; *model training*; *deployment*; *operationalization*) following established principles of terminological harmonization (Temmerman, 2000). The resulting harmonized vocabulary spans all major lifecycle phases and includes both high-frequency head terms (e.g., *development* (Grum et al., 2023), *inference* (Gossart, 2015), *production* (Georgiou et al., 2022), *power consumption* (García-Martín et al., 2019)) and strategically important low-frequency tail terms occurring only twice in the corpus (e.g., *approximate computing*, *green data centers*, *on device learning*).

Quantitatively, the consolidated set exhibits a median occurrence of four articles per term, indicating substantial variability in corpus-wide coverage and the presence of a pronounced long-tail distribution. This harmonized vocabulary serves as the methodological foundation for all subsequent quantitative analyses, including frequency distributions, lifecycle coverage evaluation, and hierarchical clustering of concept co-occurrence (see Table F.6 for the excerpt term list, grouping rationale, and statistical profiles). It also enables the computation of composite salience scores and lifecycle phase balance metrics, as described in step 2.

Step 2—Quantitative analysis of lifecycle terms.

Normalized term frequencies (per 1,000 words) were calculated for all lifecycle-related vocabulary items extracted in step 1. To prioritize terms, a composite salience score was derived that combines three factors: length-adjusted frequency, dispersion across the corpus (Juilland’s D), and temporal growth (the standardized slope of yearly frequency trends). The separation between high- and low-frequency terms was determined using a piecewise regression “elbow” on the rank-frequency curve, thereby avoiding arbitrary thresholds. Two comparative bar charts clearly illustrate the resulting distribution: head terms (more than eight occurrences; Figure F.8) and tail terms (eight or fewer occurrences; Figure F.9).

The head panel is dominated by training- and deployment concepts (e.g., *model training, deployment, inference, power consumption*). This distribution indicates a strong concentration of attention in a few of compute-oriented lifecycle terms, while infrastructure, supply-chain, and end-of-life topics remain less frequently represented.

In contrast, the long tail emphasizes infrastructure and end-of-life topics: *dynamic voltage and frequency scaling, DVFS*, power capping and carbon-aware scheduling for inference, renewable-energy integration and green data centers for infrastructure, supplier transparency and conflict minerals for provisioning, and remanufacturing or e-waste pathways for end-of-life. These terms occur less frequently, but they indicate infrastructure, supply-chain, and end-of-life topics that are present in the corpus. Training and deployment remain more visible, whereas supply-chain and end-of-life aspects are represented more weakly. This pattern indicates a stronger focus on computational efficiency than on material sourcing and post-use recovery.

Step 3—Visualization of lifecycle terms.

Building on the previous step, step 3 adds a temporal perspective via a chronological heatmap. The 34 most frequent harmonized lifecycle terms

were coded as present/absent per article under the step 1 rules and arranged with rows strictly ordered by article publication year (Table F.7). To preserve semantic neighborhoods and enable direct comparative analysis across related figures, the column order follows the dendrogram leaf order in Figure D.6 and aligns consistently with the structured lifecycle phase aggregation in Table D.3.

This dual ordering preserves temporal comparability (rows) and semantic proximity (columns), allowing for longitudinal trend detection while maintaining the structural relationships revealed in step 4. Three main patterns emerge from the heatmap. First, a *compute-centric* focus dominates early contributions (pre-2020), with the most frequent columns being *development* (39 sources), *inference* (35), and *production* (33), while upstream phases (e.g., *raw material extraction*) and downstream impacts (e.g., *disposal*, 11) remain underrepresented. Second, coverage breadth increases noticeably recently: several 2024-2025 articles reach per-source coverage values of $\omega \in [14, 20]$, compared to $\omega \leq 8$ for many pre-2020 articles. This reflects a gradual broadening from narrow, compute-heavy scopes toward more holistic lifecycle considerations. Third, columns for measurement-governance indicators with direct bearing on environmental accounting (e.g., emission-factor disclosure, supplier traceability/auditability) and end-of-life levers (reuse, repair, recycling) exhibit late-onset, low-persistence patterns—long runs of zeros punctuated by isolated activations in 2024-2025. In Table F.7, the matrix contains $\sum = 640$ filled cells, yielding a fill rate of $\frac{640}{34 \times N_{\text{sources}}}$; sparsity is concentrated in upstream (provisioning/supply chain) and downstream (end-of-life) columns, whereas training/inference columns maintain continuous coverage over time. Recent contributions increase per-source coverage ω and add operations/hardware facets, but these gains remain column-local and do not close the upstream/downstream gap (Eilam et al., 2023; Barbierato and Gatti, 2024). The chronological mapping therefore corroborates the compute-centric overhang; step 5 aggregates these columns into subphases where prevalence remains low relative to training/deployment and quantifies the shortfall at phase the level.

Step 4—Hierarchical structuring via dendrograms.

To address the identified gap between isolated term usage and holistic lifecycle conceptualization, the dendrogram-based structuring advances from binary co-occurrence data to a lifecycle-oriented ontology. Leveraging agglomerative hierarchical clustering (Rokach and Maimon, 2005) with a Jaccard distance metric, conceptual proximities between the harmonized life-

cycle terms are extracted and visualized as dendrograms. Unlike flat frequency tables, this method preserves hierarchical term relations and exposes structural clusters even in sparsely represented lifecycle phases. The first dendrogram reconstructs the general body of knowledge as a synthesis of AI lifecycle phases from the literature corpus, while the second extends this scaffold into the proposed Green AI lifecycle (Figure D.6), integrating additional upstream (e.g., *responsible resource sourcing*) and downstream (e.g., *circular AI maintenance*) phases, as well as green end-of-life and AI circularity topics.

Juxtaposing the two dendrograms surfaces two concrete shifts:

(1) Measurement- and governance-related terms with direct impact—accounting roles (e.g., emission-factor disclosure, metering/calibration logs, Power Usage Effectiveness [PUE], and Water Usage Effectiveness [WUE]) no longer sit as peripheral annotations to training/inference; in the Green AI structure, they align as a cross-cutting spine linking provisioning/siting to deployment/operation, thereby bridging hardware/infrastructure with model-centric phases. (2) Upstream and downstream subphases that are terminal leaves in the traditional map—*disposal, remanufacturing, supply-chain transparency*—co-cluster with provisioning phases (*responsible material sourcing, low-impact manufacturing, green logistics*) in the Green AI dendrogram. This co-clustering identifies supply-chain and end-of-life as quantifiable leverage points. Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) and supplier audits (e.g., cobalt and tantalum traceability) translate procurement into verifiable inventories; downstream, structured take-back programs, component-level repair, and certified recycling can contribute to reducing embodied CO₂ emissions and dependence on virgin material extraction. Training/inference columns show sustained coverage, while provisioning/supply-chain and end-of-life clusters remain sparse and late-emerging. The shared leaf order furnishes a fixed column basis for the phase aggregation in Table D.3 and for quantifying the resulting imbalances. However, both perspectives remain rooted in individual term occurrences or clustered concepts. To move from micro-level lexical analysis to a macro-level assessment of lifecycle documentation, it is necessary to aggregate terms into their corresponding phases and measure coverage breadth. This is addressed in step 5 and step 6. So, step 5 acts as the bridge between qualitative term coding and quantitative phase-level assessment, consolidating the fragmented term-level findings into a structured lifecycle map.

Figure D.6: Comparison of general body of knowledge of AI lifecycle and transition to the Green AI lifecycle as dendrograms.

Step 5—Phase-level mapping and coverage matrix.

To enable a more holistic assessment, all harmonized terms from step 1 were aggregated into their corresponding subphase and phase categories within the proposed Green AI lifecycle ontology (Figure D.6). This aggregation collapses heterogeneous terminology into a structured set of 33 subphases nested under five high-level phases, ensuring that coverage analysis reflects substantive lifecycle dimensions rather than isolated lexical choices and explicitly accommodates upstream supply-chain and downstream end-of-life processes.

For each of the 43 reviewed articles, a binary coding was applied at the subphase level (\checkmark = criterion explicitly addressed; empty cell = not addressed), based on explicit mention and operational treatment of at least one associated term within the article’s scope. This coding yields a rectangular coverage matrix (*Source* \times *Subphase*), where columns represent the 33 subphases (grouped under their five parent phases) and rows represent individual articles ordered chronologically. The resulting phase-level heatmap (Tab. D.3) is fully aligned with the dendrogram leaf order from step 4, maintaining visual and semantic continuity across term-, cluster-, and phase-level views while supporting longitudinal comparison across the entire corpus.

A \checkmark is recorded only when a subphase is evidenced by *operational content*: a concrete method/lever (e.g., dynamic voltage and frequency scaling, DVFS/power capping, carbon-aware routing), a quantitative metric with unit and declared scope/provenance (e.g., energy in J/kWh; CO₂ emission in kg using stated emission factors), or an implemented procedure with reproducible configuration/results.

Pure narrative mentions, problem statements, or policy aspirations without method/measurement are not coded; ambiguous cases are treated as missing (no \checkmark) and documented in the audit log with detailed explanatory rationale provided. The rightmost column (Σ) counts fulfilled subphases per source; the bottom row (*Total per Criterion*) counts sources per subphase. This makes coverage breadth comparable across studies and phases, explicitly highlighting gaps, biases, and persistent imbalances in lifecycle phase attention.

Step 6—Statistical analysis of lifecycle coverage.

To quantify coverage, the phase-level source-subphase matrix (Table D.3) was evaluated using three pre-specified metrics: *criterion prevalence* (percentage of sources explicitly addressing a subphase), *per-phase mean coverage* (average share of subphases addressed within a phase), and *overall lifecycle breadth* (ω) (mean number of fulfilled criteria per reviewed source).

(1) *Criterion prevalence*—the percentage of sources consistently addressing a given subphase, corresponding to the *Total per Criterion* row normalized by the corpus size; (2) *Per-phase mean coverage*—the average share of distinct subphases addressed per phase across all sources (*Mean per Phase %*); and (3) *Overall lifecycle breadth*—the mean number of distinct fulfilled criteria per source, reported in the rightmost column (ω).

The aggregated results reveal strong imbalances. Deployment-related phases (*efficient model training and testing*, *energy-aware inference*) exhibit the highest mean coverage rates, reaching up to 39.5%. Hardware-oriented phases—*responsible material sourcing* and *green logistics*—achieved 36.7 % coverage, exceeding *Green AI development* (24.0 %) and *circular AI maintenance* (22.1 %), while *green end-of-life and AI circularity* remained lowest at 17.1 %. These metrics corroborate the term-frequency analysis from step 2, confirming that lexical underrepresentation translates into structural lifecycle blind spots. Low-salience yet strategically crucial subphases—such as *circular recycling* and *green compliance*—emerge as priority levers for future Green AI research and policy alignment.

Taken together, steps 5 and 6 close the methodological loop: from raw terminology to structured, phase-level coverage analysis, supporting defensible, evidence-based prioritization of underrepresented lifecycle phases and providing clear targets for advancing a genuinely end-to-end Green AI agenda.

Table D.3: Phase-level heatmap of the Green AI lifecycle. The heatmap ranges from blue-white-red. A check mark (✓) indicates that a criterion is addressed in the corresponding article. The rightmost column (Σ) reports the number of fulfilled criteria per source, while the bottom row (*total per criterion*) shows how many sources address each criterion. Background shading highlights aggregate rows for readability. Columns follow the dendrogram leaf order (Figure D.6) and the term-level heatmap (Table F.7), with consistent colour codes and phase patterns to ensure cross-figure comparability. In addition to coverage per phase (%), it reports the mean number of fulfilled criteria per phase and per article.

Synthesis	1) Green hardware selection and infrastructure design	2) Green AI development	3) Low-footprint AI task realization	4) Circular AI maintenance and green administration	5) Green end-of-life and AI circularity	
Source	1.1) Responsible material sourcing 1.2) Low-impact manufacturing 1.3) Green logistics 1.4) Energy-aware infrastructure 1.5) Incoming supply chain transpar.	2.1) Goal setting, business understanding 2.2) AI validation and non-AI alternative 2.3) Low-carbon data acquisition 2.4) Green AI design modeling 2.5) Transparent AI documentation 2.6) AI system implementation and eval. 2.7) Efficient model training and test. 2.8) Efficient hyperparameter tuning 2.9) Green model fine-tuning 2.10) Lifecycle-aware AI system eval. 2.11) Continuous integration and delivery 2.12) Carbon-aware model compression 2.13) Responsible Green AI	3.1) Green deployment 3.2) Energy-aware inference 3.3) Inference optimization 3.4) Green AI operations 3.5) Run-time, simulation, and reg. AI scns.	4.1) Proactive model monitoring 4.2) Green compliance 4.3) Benchmarking with alternatives 4.4) Continuous improvement	5.1) AI model reutilization 5.2) Resource recovery 5.3) Circular recycling 5.4) AI model archivation 5.5) AI model disposal 5.6) Outgoing supply chain transpar.	Σ
(Gossart, 2015)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	7
(Batra et al., 2018)	✓ ✓		✓		✓	1
(Lacoste et al., 2019)	✓ ✓		✓		✓	7
(Wu et al., 2019)	✓ ✓		✓		✓	7
(Henderson et al., 2020)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	9
(Anthony et al., 2020)	✓ ✓		✓		✓	8
(Schwartz et al., 2020)	✓ ✓		✓		✓	6
(Trébaol, 2020)	✓ ✓		✓		✓	6
(Strubell et al., 2020)	✓ ✓		✓		✓	4
(Hernandez and Brown, 2020)	✓ ✓		✓		✓	3
(Haakman et al., 2021)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	15
(Xu et al., 2021)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	11
(Li et al., 2021)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	10
(Patterson et al., 2021)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	10
(Van Wynsberghe, 2021)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	7
(Bammour et al., 2021)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	7
(Lannelongue et al., 2021)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	6
(Cao et al., 2021)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	5
(Shaikh et al., 2021)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	3
(Wu et al., 2022)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	13
(Kaack et al., 2022)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	13
(Ligzat et al., 2022)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	10
(Dodge et al., 2022)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	9
(Robbins and Van Wynsberghe, 2022)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	7
(Georgiou et al., 2022)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	6
(Gupta et al., 2022)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	5
(Patterson et al., 2022)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	5
(Verdecchia et al., 2023)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	16
(Zhou et al., 2023)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	14
(Menghani, 2023)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	12
(Chen et al., 2023)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	10
(Tornede et al., 2023)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	12
(Luccioni et al., 2023)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	10
(Eilam et al., 2023)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	10
(Li et al., 2023)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	7
(Bouza et al., 2023)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	5
(Grum et al., 2023)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	4
(Barbierato and Gatti, 2024)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	16
(Bolíu-Canedo et al., 2024)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	15
(Longpre et al., 2024)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	14
(Alzoubi and Mishra, 2024)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	13
(Grum and Gronau, 2024)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	10
(Wright et al., 2025)	✓ ✓	✓	✓		✓	10
Total per Phase	79	134	85	38	44	380
Mean per Phase (in %)	36.7%	24.0%	39.5%	22.1%	17.1%	—
Total per Criterion	0 34 37 8 0	1 8 25 2 5 2 28 13 14 8 1 20 7	26 36 14 5 4	16 0 17 5	17 2 6 11 8 0	380
Share of all fulfilled subphase codings (in %)	0 9 10 2 0	0 2 7 1 1 1 7 3 4 2 0 6 2	7 9 4 1 1 1	4 0 4 1 1	4 1 2 3 2 0	100

Appendix D.2. Quantitative assessment of lifecycle phase representation

Based on the five review-derived Green AI phases and 33 subphase categories, the following analysis presents a review-derived analytical lifecycle structure that organizes recurring lifecycle activities identified in the literature. It is used as a transparent analytical structuring device rather than as a prescriptive process model. The analysis indicates an overemphasis on training- and inference-related topics, while upstream provisioning, logistics, and recycling-related topics remain underrepresented.

Table D.3 consolidates 43 reviewed contributions, mapping upstream activities (e.g., raw material sourcing, manufacturing), core compute phases (e.g., model training, inference), and downstream activities (e.g., deployment, end-of-life). While training and inference dominate coverage across nearly all studies, upstream phases—particularly raw material extraction, component manufacturing, and transport—receive limited attention despite disproportionate Scope 3 impacts. Cross-cutting governance dimensions, including supply chain traceability, compliance auditing, and Green AI principles, emerge only sporadically, underscoring the fragmented and uneven integration of Green AI across the reviewed literature.

To assess these patterns, all harmonized lifecycle terms from step 1 were aggregated into 33 subphases grouped under five phases (Figure D.6). A binary coverage matrix (*source* \times *subphase*) coded whether each reviewed article addressed a subphase explicitly. This phase-level mapping (Tab. D.3) enables visual comparison of coverage breadth across studies, revealing a strong bias toward compute- and deployment-oriented subphases.

Quantitative analysis (step 6) confirms these imbalances. The *mean per phase (%)* values are: *low-footprint AI task realization* 39.5%, *green hardware selection and infrastructure design* 36.7%, *Green AI development* 24.0%, *circular AI maintenance and green administration* 22.1%, and *green end-of-life and AI circularity* 17.1%. *Low-footprint AI task realization* and *green hardware selection and infrastructure design* are most frequently analyzed, *Green AI development* and *circular AI maintenance and green administration* moderately, while *green end-of-life and AI circularity* attracts little coverage. Both the *total per criterion* row and the ω column confirm that impactful subphases like *green compliance* and *outgoing supply chain transparency* remain overlooked leverage points.

The results demonstrate an entrenched focus on compute-related phases, while embodied impacts, recycling pathways, and governance-related aspects remain comparatively neglected. This imbalance underscores the need for

a more comprehensive, lifecycle-oriented perspective on Green AI beyond efficiency-centered narratives.

The distribution of energy and material burdens concentrates on training and inference, while several upstream activities, such as raw material sourcing, logistics, and selected manufacturing aspects, as well as downstream stages such as recycling or landfill disposal, remain weakly represented or inconsistently integrated into impact assessment.

Upstream phases—from bauxite mining and silicon wafer production to accelerator board assembly—are dominated by embodied emissions tied to electricity-intensive smelting, ultrapure water use, and globalized supply chains. Case studies show that these impacts, especially rare-earth extraction and chip packaging, can outweigh runtime energy when hardware replacement intervals fall below three years (Schwartz et al., 2020; Patterson et al., 2021).

Core computing phases—notably multi-terabyte dataset staging, GPU-intensive training of transformer architectures, large-scale hyperparameter sweeps, and latency-critical inference pipelines—account for the majority of direct electricity use in AI systems, with training runs often measured in megawatt-hours (Schwartz et al., 2020; Patterson et al., 2021). While training remains the single most energy-intensive peak activity (particularly for frontier-scale transformer models), sustained inference across heterogeneous environments (cloud clusters, embedded edge devices, and end-user hardware) often exceeds training in cumulative consumption over deployment lifetimes (Patterson et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2022; Wright et al., 2025). Upstream data-handling processes, especially massive preprocessing and archival storage of high-volume datasets, also impose substantial environmental burdens that are frequently underestimated in carbon accounting (Henderson et al., 2020; Schwartz et al., 2020).

Downstream and cross-cutting phases—including deployment pipelines, runtime inference services, continuous monitoring infrastructures, and end-of-life management of hardware—show lower energy intensity per transaction but accumulate substantial impacts due to high query volumes and persistent operation in production. End-of-life activities such as component reuse, rare-earth recovery, and certified recycling are rarely quantified with methodological rigor, yet remain decisive for mitigating embodied carbon and material scarcity (Ligozat et al., 2022; Grum and Gronau, 2024).

Appendix D.3. Synthesizing Green AI lifecycle phases

Building on the clustered terms, the harmonized vocabulary was mapped onto a five-phase Green AI lifecycle that spans hardware, software, and operational stages, using the dendrogram leaf order to assign terms to phase-specific subphases: (1) *Green hardware selection and infrastructure design* (provisioning, siting, data-centre operations), (2) *Green AI development* (architecture/design, training setup, evaluation), (3) *Low-footprint AI task realization* (placement, batching, serving), (4) *Circular AI maintenance and green administration* (monitoring, updates, retraining triggers), (5) *Green end-of-life and AI circularity* (take-back, repair/reuse, recycling). This structure improves targeted assessment: training- and inference-oriented improvements are well represented (García-Martín et al., 2019; Patterson et al., 2021), whereas end-of-life flows such as hardware recycling remain sparsely evidenced (Alzoubi and Mishra, 2024). The following section details each phase, beginning with process synthesis and system definition as the basis for subsequent steps.

System definition

The main phases synthesized from the literature corpus are clarified in the following first. Their subphase tasks are clarified thereafter.

1. Green hardware selection and infrastructure design. The *green hardware selection and infrastructure design* phase addresses upstream impacts often hidden in model-centric discussions but dominate full LCAs. It covers responsible sourcing of raw materials (e.g., cobalt, lithium, rare earth elements for batteries and GPUs), low-impact semiconductor manufacturing processes (e.g., extreme ultraviolet lithography with reduced water and energy intensity), and the carbon footprint of chip packaging and assembly. Empirical evidence indicates that embodied emissions from mining, wafer fabrication, and board integration can exceed the operational footprint of smaller-scale AI deployments if amortized over short hardware lifetimes (Henderson et al., 2020; Ligozat et al., 2022). Large-scale open models such as BLOOM demonstrate that pre-use stages account for several hundred tons of CO₂e, underlining the non-triviality of hardware supply chains (Luccioni et al., 2023). Production concentrated in few regions (e.g., Taiwan, South Korea) creates supply-chain fragility and carbon-intensive logistics. Water-intensive fabrication in scarcity regions (e.g., Arizona, Taiwan) links hardware to local stressors beyond carbon. Green logistics targets low-carbon transport and optimized data-center siting to cut shipping distances

and grid emissions (Gupta et al., 2022). Finally, energy-aware infrastructure levers—such as dynamic voltage and frequency scaling (DVFS) and renewable-powered data-center siting—connect embodied and operational perspectives by extending hardware lifetimes and reducing emissions during use (Alzoubi and Mishra, 2024). These mechanisms underline that hardware considerations are an important determinant of AI’s ecological footprint.

2. Green AI development. The *Green AI development* phase targets Green AI in algorithmic design and training workflows, complementing hardware-focused measures. It covers low-carbon data acquisition, green model architectures, transparent documentation, and lifecycle-aware evaluation, alongside efficient training, hyperparameter tuning, fine-tuning, and carbon-conscious model compression. These activities dominate the energy footprint of AI because dataset preparation, iterative experimentation, and large-scale parameter searches are computationally intensive (Chen et al., 2023; Zhou et al., 2023). Recent work stresses the importance of embedding Green AI constraints directly into development pipelines, e.g., through energy-proportional architectures, carbon-aware scheduling of training jobs, and standardized reporting of dataset and model choices (Schwartz et al., 2020; Henderson et al., 2020; Grum and Gronau, 2024; Longpre et al., 2024). Traditional lifecycle models often ignore the cumulative impact of repeated trials and ablation studies, although these can exceed the footprint of the final model deployment. Evidence from application domains such as fintech illustrates that fast iteration cycles amplify this burden (Haakman et al., 2021). Explicitly integrating Green AI principles at the development stage is therefore essential to balance accuracy gains with measurable reductions in environmental cost.

3. Low-footprint AI task realization. The *low-footprint AI task realization* phase involves transferring AI models from the development environment into real-world production settings where they serve diverse end-users or operational systems. This phase covers deployment, real-time inference, on-device learning, edge computing, and fog computing, emphasizing strategies that reduce operational energy consumption and carbon emissions. During deployment, model pipelines should be integrated with monitoring infrastructures that track latency, accuracy drift, and energy consumption in real time. This operational telemetry enables adaptive scaling, targeted retraining, and selective activation of components, directly linking performance management with environmental cost control. Recent work discusses monitoring, deployment, and energy-aware operational choices as relevant levers for reducing

inference-related energy demand in production settings, although reported savings remain context-dependent and are not directly generalizable (Haakman et al., 2021; Grum, 2022). Studies highlight that such hybrid architectures yield measurable reductions in water and carbon footprints while maintaining Service Level Agreement (SLA) compliance, making deployment a decisive Green AI lever (Verdecchia et al., 2023).

4. Circular AI maintenance and green administration. The *circular AI maintenance and green administration* phase emphasizes retraining models with updated data, replacing only degraded components, and reusing accelerators across projects to reduce embodied emissions. Core activities include continuous performance and drift monitoring, targeted retraining to counter dataset shift, and refactoring of inefficient model components to reduce computational demand. Maintenance also covers patching vulnerabilities, pruning redundant parameters, and recalibrating models under new workload or regulatory conditions, thereby avoiding premature redevelopment. Empirical studies indicate that lifecycle costs can be dominated by repeated retraining and inefficient update cycles if models are not systematically maintained (Patterson et al., 2021). Circular maintenance instead emphasizes resource-aware updates that preserve accuracy while reducing marginal energy use, e.g., selective fine-tuning on critical subsets or modular replacement of underperforming components. Moreover, transparent logging of monitoring metrics and maintenance actions enables auditable traceability of improvements, facilitating replication and compliance (Alzoubi and Mishra, 2024). By maximizing reuse and adaptability, this phase mitigates the environmental burden of frequent redeployment and aligns AI practice with broader circular economy strategies.

5. Green end-of-life and AI circularity. The *green end-of-life and AI circularity* phase covers retirement and material recovery of AI infrastructure, including servers, accelerators, and networking equipment. Central tasks involve standardized decommissioning, component-level sorting for rare earths, cobalt, and palladium, and refurbishment routes documented through certification schemes. Yet, empirical evidence shows that roughly 80% of electronic waste bypasses formal recycling, handled instead in informal markets with severe ecological consequences (Ligozat et al., 2022). AI-specific barriers include missing disclosure of bill-of-materials, inconsistent component provenance, and absent inventory systems for tracking reuse cycles. Policy-driven measures such as producer-responsibility mandates, carbon- and material-labeled devices, and integration with ISO-compliant LCA reporting could

help address these gaps and improve the auditability of embodied impacts at scale.

Subphase tasks

1.1) Responsible material sourcing. This subphase covers environmental impacts arising from raw material extraction and resource procurement, including embodied emissions in hardware supply chains (Gupta et al., 2022; Henderson et al., 2020). Embedding responsible sourcing principles at this stage enables early and proactive mitigation of the ecological footprint of AI hardware supply chains, representing a perspective reflected in recent literature.

1.2) Low-impact manufacturing. This phase involves transforming raw materials into hardware components through energy- and emission-aware production processes (Ligozat et al., 2022). It emphasizes manufacturing innovations that substantially reduce embodied carbon and waste generation (factors that traditional AI lifecycle models frequently overlook). Recent LCA studies (Gupta et al., 2022; Luccioni et al., 2023) indicate that Scope 3 emissions from semiconductor manufacturing and assembly can form a substantial share of overall hardware footprints, depending on device type, utilization, and replacement cycles. These findings collectively underscore the necessity of integrating verifiable low-impact manufacturing strategies—such as renewable-powered fabrication, material efficiency, and closed-loop recycling—directly within Green AI paradigms.

1.3) Green logistics. The *green logistics* subphase highlights that most accelerators and server boards are produced in East Asia and shipped to North America or Europe, creating long supply chains with concentrated carbon hotspots in maritime and aviation links. Beyond intercontinental flows, regional distribution and repeated packaging of components amplify embodied impacts that remain poorly documented in Green AI assessments (Ligozat et al., 2022). Green practices include optimized multimodal routing, modal shifts from air to sea or rail, shipment consolidation, and the use of electric or hydrogen-powered fleets. Empirical assessments show that transport can represent a non-trivial share of embodied emissions, especially when production is concentrated in East Asia with long supply chains to North America or Europe (Zhou et al., 2023). Incorporating logistics into lifecycle models therefore closes a persistent blind spot in Green AI analysis and highlights siting strategies that reduce both distances and grid-related

operational emissions.

1.4) Energy-aware infrastructure. This phase addresses the design and operation of infrastructure supporting AI hardware, such as data centers and network facilities, with particular emphasis on renewable energy use, high energy efficiency, advanced cooling technologies, and intelligent resource management. It complements the hardware lifecycle by capturing ongoing operational impacts and by making infrastructure-level conditions explicit, which remain a critical yet still insufficiently addressed dimension in conventional AI lifecycle models (Patterson et al., 2021; Alzoubi and Mishra, 2024).

1.5) Incoming supply chain transparency. The subphase considers material origin and component inputs in hardware manufacturing. It covers traceability of resources such as semiconductors and rare earth materials across supplier tiers and the use of environmental data before fabrication (Gupta et al., 2022).

2.1) Goal setting and business understanding. Infrastructure readiness, stakeholder roles, and Green AI targets are determined in concert, while potential risks, fairness, and compliance concerns are addressed early (Ligozat et al., 2022; MathWorks, 2024). Embedding these guardrails from inception can help structure downstream lifecycle activities and facilitates transparent monitoring.

2.2) AI validation and non-AI alternative check. The *AI validation and non-AI alternative check* phase typically involves analyzing and evaluating how traditional systems or simpler algorithms (which may not involve ML or AI) handle the problem at hand. It is about gathering empirical evidence on the feasibility, efficiency, and limitations of existing, non-AI approaches to solving the problem, and using this information to identify where AI might be applied more effectively (Ligozat et al., 2022; Grum and Gronau, 2024).

2.3) Low-carbon data acquisition, collection, and preparation. Recognizing that data acquisition and processing contribute significantly to AI’s carbon footprint (Verdecchia et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2023), this phase focuses on sustainable practices such as selective sampling, noise reduction, and de-duplication to reduce dataset size and processing energy. Standard AI lifecycle models often treat data acquisition superficially; by embedding carbon-awareness into data pipelines, Green AI development effectively curtails unnecessary computational burdens early in the lifecycle (Henderson et al., 2020).

2.4) Green AI design modeling. Designing Green AI models involves

balancing computational complexity and performance, adopting energy-efficient architectures, and leveraging modular designs to facilitate reuse and compression (Grum and Gronau, 2024; Longpre et al., 2024). This architectural approach extends beyond typical AI design by embedding lifecycle emissions considerations at the conceptual stage.

2.5) Transparent AI documentation. This phase mandates documentation of design decisions, energy consumption, and environmental impacts, thereby supporting reproducibility, accountability, and informed auditing (Alzoubi and Mishra, 2024; Grum and Gronau, 2024). Transparency fosters shared community standards and supports regulatory compliance (dimensions that classical lifecycle models insufficiently emphasize).

2.6) AI system implementation and evaluation. The *AI system implementation and evaluation* phase involves taking the theoretical model and implementing it in code, creating the necessary software infrastructure, and integrating the model into the larger technical environment. The implementation phase ensures that the AI model works effectively within its intended operational setting. This includes setting up the required infrastructure, such as choosing the appropriate hardware, configuring servers, and connecting the model to databases or APIs it will interact with (Grum, 2022; Ligozat et al., 2022).

2.7) Efficient model training and testing. Model training is computationally intensive and a major source of AI’s carbon emissions (Patterson et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2023). Green AI integrates training improvements such as dynamic resource allocation, adaptive batch sizing, and early stopping to reduce energy use without compromising accuracy (García-Martín et al., 2019). This refinement addresses a critical environmental challenge absent in traditional lifecycle definitions.

2.8) Efficient hyperparameter tuning. Hyperparameter tuning can require extensive training iterations, leading to high-energy costs (Verdecchia et al., 2023; Zhou et al., 2023). Green AI proposes approaches including multi-fidelity optimization and surrogate modeling to minimize redundant computations, representing a distinct methodological layer of Green AI integration within the AI development process.

2.9) Green model fine-tuning. Fine-tuning pre-trained models is a cost-effective alternative to full retraining but still contributes to emissions. Green fine-tuning techniques (including pruning, quantization, and task-adaptive retraining) reduce energy use while maintaining or improving performance (Alzoubi and Mishra, 2024; Longpre et al., 2024).

2.10) Lifecycle-aware AI system evaluation. Evaluating AI models extends beyond accuracy metrics to include environmental impact assessments across the model’s lifecycle (Ligozat et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2023). This holistic evaluation facilitates informed trade-offs between Green AI considerations and performance, a perspective not consistently addressed in classical AI evaluation approaches.

2.11) Continuous integration and delivery. In the *continuous integration and delivery* phase, ML models and code are regularly integrated into shared repositories, with automated tests ensuring that updates do not disrupt existing functionality or degrade system performance. This process helps identify issues early, reducing the risk of errors during the later stages of model deployment. In continuous delivery, once models pass automated testing, they are automatically deployed to production environments (MathWorks, 2024).

2.12) Carbon-aware model compression. This subphase addresses pruning, quantization, and knowledge distillation techniques that cut parameter counts and FLOPs during inference (Chen et al., 2023; Verdecchia et al., 2023). Empirical benchmarks indicate that quantization-aware training and structured pruning can reduce inference energy, memory access, and latency in some settings, although the magnitude of savings and possible accuracy effects remain workload- and hardware-dependent. Compression also delays the need for high-end accelerators, decreasing embodied emissions from frequent hardware refreshes. Embedding compression systematically into the lifecycle therefore couples design-level interventions with measurable carbon savings across deployment and retraining cycles.

2.13) Responsible Green AI. *Responsible Green AI* integrates Green AI with broader principles of responsible AI, including fairness, privacy, accountability, transparency, human oversight, and social inclusion (Schwartz et al., 2020). This cross-cutting phase ensures that ecological objectives are pursued without compromising ethical obligations, recognizing that genuine Green AI requires balancing environmental, societal, and technical considerations in AI design, deployment, and governance. By embedding these values into Green AI strategies, responsible Green AI highlights that ecological gains should align with trustworthiness and human-centered AI, reinforcing compliance with emerging global guidelines such as the OECD AI Principles and the EU AI Act.

3.1) Green deployment. The *green deployment* phase covers the transition of AI models from development into production while explicitly min-

imizing the environmental footprint of integration and inference. It involves carefully selecting infrastructures (e.g., edge devices, hybrid cloud-edge) based on lifecycle-aware energy and carbon performance, optimizing software-hardware matching, and supporting adaptive resource scaling under variable loads (Verdecchia et al., 2023). Embedding Green AI criteria into deployment planning addresses a key gap in conventional lifecycles, where deployment is often reduced to a purely technical decision.

3.2) Energy-aware inference. The *energy-aware inference* phase focuses on reducing the energy intensity of prediction workloads without sacrificing model accuracy. While inference typically consumes less energy per inference than training, its high execution frequency in real-world systems can result in substantial cumulative impacts (Verdecchia et al., 2022). Inference energy can be reduced by applying mixed-precision kernels on GPUs, dynamically deactivating unused attention heads, and adjusting batch sizes to match accelerator memory bandwidth without exceeding latency constraints. Comparative analyses of inference energy versus training emissions remain an open research challenge, requiring harmonized metrics to enable consistent benchmarking.

3.3) Inference optimization. The *inference optimization* phase minimizes energy and latency during model serving through quantization, pruning, and adaptive computation (Henderson et al., 2020; Ligozat et al., 2022). Hardware-software co-tuning leverages carbon-aware scheduling and dynamic voltage and frequency scaling to align inference workloads with low-carbon power availability (Gupta et al., 2022; Patterson et al., 2022). As shown by Luccioni et al. (2023), sustained inference phases often dominate lifecycle energy use, reinforcing the need for continuous efficiency monitoring within deployed architectures (Schwartz et al., 2020; Patterson et al., 2021).

3.4) Green AI operations. *Green AI operations* span runtime practices that extend beyond initial deployment, including accuracy preservation under shifting data distributions, adaptive retraining triggers, and hardware-level telemetry for thermal and power anomalies (Grum, 2022). Central mechanisms involve lightweight monitoring pipelines coupled with DVFS-based throttling, queue-aware load balancing across heterogeneous nodes, and carbon-aware job scheduling linked to grid mix variability. By explicitly integrating these operational levers, the subphase connects reliability engineering with ecological accountability, ensuring that inference workloads remain both performant and resource-efficient across the system’s full-service horizon.

3.5) Run-time, simulation, and regular AI sensitivity assessment. In the *run-time simulation and regular AI sensitivity assessment* phase, the focus is on verifying that the model sustains its accuracy and reliability over time in practical settings. This involves monitoring for performance decline, detecting shifts in data distribution, and managing hardware issues. Regular evaluations help maintain system stability and improve overall performance (Grum, 2022).

4.1) Proactive model monitoring and scorecard creation. The *proactive model monitoring and scorecard creation* subphase extends conventional monitoring pipelines by coupling accuracy and latency metrics with energy, carbon, and thermal telemetry (Verdecchia et al., 2023). Runtime dashboards integrate readings from hardware counters (e.g., Running Average Power Limit, RAPL; performance monitoring counters, PMCs), rack-level meters, and carbon-intensity APIs to detect efficiency drifts under real workloads. Early-warning triggers initiate corrective actions such as adaptive batching, or workload migration to greener nodes, thereby linking operational reliability with continuous Green AI assurance throughout the inference lifecycle.

4.2) Green compliance. The *green compliance* subphase addresses binding and voluntary frameworks by embedding environmental requirements into procurement, design, and reporting workflows (Alzoubi and Mishra, 2024). Compliance mechanisms include third-party verified carbon disclosure protocols (e.g., Carbon Disclosure Project, CDP; Greenhouse Gas, GHG Protocol), lifecycle reporting aligned with ISO 50001, and audit trails linking AI workloads to renewable energy purchase agreements (Power Purchase Agreement, PPAs; and Renewable Energy Certificates, RECs). For data centers, verification may extend to Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE) metrics and regional grid mix disclosure. By documenting boundary choices, and allocation rules, Green Compliance establishes auditability and comparability, while reducing exposure to greenwashing claims.

4.3) Benchmarking with alternatives (AI and non-AI techniques). The focus of model benchmarking lies in identifying the most efficient models, whether AI-based or non-AI, by comparing their performance on standardized benchmarks (such as evaluating their energy consumption or training methods) (Grum, 2022).

4.4) Continuous improvement. The *continuous improvement* subphase establishes structured feedback loops where monitoring results trigger

targeted interventions such as selective retraining on drifting data, parameter-efficient fine-tuning, or modular reconfiguration of components (Grum, 2022). Improvements are validated not only against accuracy but also performance-environmental thresholds and phase completion criteria thresholds, ensuring environmental objectives remain binding constraints. Techniques like low-rank adaptation, dynamic sparsification, and lifecycle-aware retraining schedules reduce overhead while preserving service quality, thereby embedding Green AI directly into the system’s optimization cycle.

5.1) AI model reutilization. The *AI model reutilization* subphase promotes extending model lifetimes through transfer learning, fine-tuning, and distillation, thereby avoiding redundant training and embodied carbon from new model development (Schwartz et al., 2020; Patterson et al., 2021). Reusing pretrained architectures across tasks leverages existing compute investments while preserving empirical performance under reduced energy budgets (Henderson et al., 2020; Ligozat et al., 2022). Lifecycle-explicit accounting further links model reuse to avoided upstream emissions in data collection and hardware provisioning, establishing reutilization as a core lever for sustainable AI deployment (Gupta et al., 2022; Patterson et al., 2022).

5.2) Resource recovery. The *resource recovery* phase targets the systematic extraction and reuse of valuable components and materials from decommissioned AI hardware (Gupta et al., 2022). This includes extending component lifespans through refurbishment, reclaiming rare earth elements, and reintroducing recovered parts into new systems. By reducing the need for virgin material extraction, resource recovery directly offsets upstream embodied emissions.

5.3) Circular recycling. *Circular recycling* extends traditional recycling by incorporating closed-loop material flows in AI hardware manufacturing (Ligozat et al., 2022). Component dismantling entails selective separation optimized for purity-driven material recovery, facilitating closed-loop reintegration into comparable-quality components. This reduces landfill dependency and supports lifecycle continuity by buffering production systems against primary-resource constraints.

5.4) AI model archivation. In the *AI model archivation phase*, decommissioned models and associated devices are catalogued, documented, and retained within traceable repositories to preserve reproducibility and institutional memory. Following Grum, such archival practice maintains access to historic configurations and underpins sustainability through reuse-oriented resource stewardship rather than hardware obsolescence (Grum, 2022).

5.5) AI model disposal. The *AI model disposal* phase marks the terminal lifecycle stage in which obsolete hardware is eliminated, frequently through non-regulated recycling, incineration, or landfilling. Such unmanaged disposal pathways negate circularity gains and perpetuate embodied-carbon and toxicity leakage. A shift toward certified dismantling and material recovery processes is critical to integrate this phase into the broader Green AI governance architecture. According to Luccioni et al. (2023), such disposal methods pose significant environmental risks due to hazardous emissions and resource loss, making sustainable disposal strategies critical (Luccioni et al., 2023).

5.6) Outgoing supply chain transparency. The *outgoing supply chain transparency* subphase complements the upstream focus by ensuring that sustainability information propagates forward through the distribution and recovery network. After AI systems or hardware leave the manufacturer, downstream partners—distributors, operators, refurbishers, recyclers—should retain access to environmental and social performance data attached to each product instance. This includes verified documentation of embodied carbon, repairability scores, and recyclability indices, which support responsible take-back schemes. Blockchain-anchored material passports and supplier scorecards enable traceable reverse logistics, ensuring that devices and components re-enter secondary material cycles instead of contributing to e-waste streams (Gupta et al., 2022).

Building on the five Green AI phases and 33 review-derived subphase categories, the next step presents an illustrative lifecycle representation that visualizes their analytical relation, including the review-derived distinction between completeness-related and threshold-related evaluation situations. The representation is included for transparency only and should not be interpreted as a validated operational process model.

Appendix E. Illustrative representation of synthesized categories

Appendix E.1. Presentation of dual model representation

For readers who prefer a higher-level and more aggregated representation, a level-0 LCA-style overview (Figure E.7) is presented alongside the level-1 notation-based illustrative lifecycle visualization. *The correspondence between Level-0 LCA phases and level-1 Green AI tasks is summarized in Table E.4.* The mapping is provided as an analytical reading aid and does

not assign phases to single LCA stages but rather illustrates typical points of interaction across stages. Dynamic, data-driven adaptations are therefore not fully captured by static LCA diagrams.

Figure E.7: Level-0 LCA-style overview as an analytical representation.

In the reviewed studies, the reduction of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions is a recurring objective. Individual Green AI tasks can be interpreted as potential levers within iterative Plan-Do-Check-Act-like cycles (Kaack et al., 2022; Verdecchia et al., 2023). Across lifecycle phases, these tasks are discussed in relation to both embodied and operational impacts, as well as performance-related trade-offs in AI systems (Patterson et al., 2022; Wright et al., 2025).

Table E.4: Illustrative mapping of Green AI task clusters (Level-1) to LCA stages (Level-0) as an analytical reading aid

LCA (Level-0)	phase	Green AI task cluster (Level-1)
Goal and scope		Boundary definition, system assumptions, and evaluation context
Inventory		Data collection, model development, deployment, and operation, contributing to inventory-related flows
Impact assessment		Interpretation of environmental indicators derived from inventory data in relation to performance trade-offs
Interpretation		Consideration of follow-up actions (e.g., adaptation or adjustment) based on observed outcomes

Appendix E.2. Illustrative adaptation and adjustment situations

Table E.5: Examples of *adapt (external)* versus *adjust (internal)* across phases

Phase	Adapt (external)	Adjust (internal)
1) Green hardware selection and infrastructure design	Switch to renewable-powered suppliers; optimise logistics windows	Redesign PCB for low-power states; firmware power caps
2) Green AI development	Schedule data pre-processing in low-carbon windows	Architecture simplification; pruning; quantization-aware training
3) Low-footprint AI task realization	Carbon-aware autoscaling; placement on greener regions	quantization; operator fusion; batch-size tuning
4) Circular AI maintenance and green administration	Renewable-powered maintenance windows	Retraining with early stopping; model distillation
5) Green end-of-life and AI circularity	Certified recycler contracts; reverse logistics	Component reuse planning; modular design for disassembly

Appendix F. Descriptive summaries of extracted results

Appendix F.1. Term consolidation and synonym grouping results

Table F.6: Excerpt from the consolidated term list

Source	Year	development	inference	production	distribution	power consumption	deployment
Gossart	2015	1	0	1	0	1	1
Batra et al.	2018	1	1	0	0	1	0
Lacoste et al.	2019	0	1	1	1	1	0
Wu et al.	2019	1	1	1	1	1	1
Anthony et al.	2020	1	1	1	0	1	0
Strubell et al.	2020	1	1	0	1	1	0
Schwartz et al.	2020	1	1	1	0	0	0
Hernandez and Brown	2020	0	1	0	0	0	0
Henderson et al.	2020	1	1	1	1	1	1
Trebaol	2020	1	0	1	1	1	1
Shaikh et al.	2021	0	0	1	0	0	1
Xu et al.	2021	1	1	1	1	1	1
Haakman et al.	2021	1	1	1	1	0	1
Bannour et al.	2021	1	1	1	1	0	1
Li et al.	2021	1	1	0	1	1	1
Patterson et al.	2021	1	1	1	1	1	0
Patterson et al.	2021	1	1	1	0	1	1
Lannelongue et al.	2021	1	0	1	1	1	0
Cao et al.	2021	0	1	0	1	1	1
Van Wynsberghe	2021	1	0	1	1	0	0
Robbins and Van Wynsberghe	2022	1	0	1	0	1	0
Ligozat et al.	2022	1	1	1	1	0	1
Dodge et al.	2022	1	1	1	0	1	1
Kaack et al.	2022	1	1	1	0	0	1
Georgiou et al.	2022	1	1	0	1	1	0
Wu et al.	2022	1	1	1	1	1	1
Gupta et al.	2022	1	1	1	0	1	0
Menghani	2023	1	1	1	1	1	1
Eilam et al.	2023	1	1	0	1	1	1
Verdecchia et al.	2023	1	1	1	1	1	1
Chen et al.	2023	1	1	0	1	0	1
Grum et al.	2023	1	0	1	1	0	0
Tornede et al.	2023	1	1	1	1	1	0
Bouza et al.	2023	1	0	1	1	1	1
Luccioni et al.	2023	1	1	1	1	1	1
Li et al.	2023	1	1	0	1	1	0
Zhou et al.	2023	1	1	1	1	1	1
Alzoubi and Mishra	2024	1	1	1	1	1	1
Longpre et al.	2024	1	1	0	1	0	1
Bolón-Canedo et al.	2024	1	1	1	1	1	1
Grum and Gronau	2024	1	1	1	1	0	0
Barbierato and Gatti	2024	1	1	1	1	1	1
Wright et al.	2025	1	1	1	1	0	1
		39	35	33	32	30	27

Appendix F.2. Bar charts of lifecycle-related terms

Appendix F.3. Terms occurring more than eight times (upper panel)

Figure F.8: Bar chart of lifecycle-related terms—**upper panel** showing terms occurring more than eight times across the corpus. These high-frequency “head” terms form the dominant lifecycle-related vocabulary, including *model training*, *deployment*, *inference*, and *power consumption*, and account for the majority of observed salience. Their prominence reflects a research focus on compute-intensive phases, as quantified in Section Appendix D.1.

Appendix F.4. Terms occurring up to eight times (lower panel)

Figure F.9: Bar chart of lifecycle-related terms—**lower panel** showing terms occurring fewer than nine times across the corpus. These low-frequency terms form the long tail of the lifecycle-related vocabulary and point to more sparsely represented aspects of Green AI, including infrastructure, governance, data handling, and end-of-life topics. Their comparatively low frequency highlights areas that remain underrepresented in the literature relative to the more prominent compute- and deployment-oriented terms discussed in Section Appendix D.1.

Appendix F.5. Heatmap of the 34 most frequent lifecycle-related terms across the reviewed articles

Table F.7: Heatmap of the 34 most frequent lifecycle-related terms across the reviewed articles. The heatmap ranges from blue to white to red. A filled cell indicates that the term (column) is explicitly addressed in the corresponding article (row). Terms are ordered according to the dendrogram leaf arrangement (Figure D.6) to ensure comparability across figures. This Table F.7 forms the basis for aggregating terms into harmonized subphases and high-level phases in the phase-level analysis (Table D.3).

Synthesis	Terms																										Σ										
Source	development	inference	production	distribution	power consumption	deployment	model training	ai model	manufacturing	efficiency	transparency	transport	privacy	accountability	reuse	benchmarking	pruning	architecture search	energy efficiency	neural architecture search	quantization	sparsity	transfer learning	data collection	hyperparameter tuning	documentation	extraction	lifecycle assessment	lighting	maintenance	refuse	model distillation	fine tuning	disposal	Σ		
(Gossart, 2015)	✓		✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓						✓																✓	12	
(Batra et al., 2018)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																							✓	6
(Wu et al., 2019)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓										✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	14	
(Lacoste et al., 2019)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															9	
(Schwartz et al., 2020)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																							14	
(Henderson et al., 2020)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															14	
(Anthony et al., 2020)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															13	
(Trébaol, 2020)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															11	
(Strubell et al., 2020)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															8	
(Hernandez and Brown, 2020)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															5	
(Patterson et al., 2021)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															19	
(Xu et al., 2021)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															19	
(Haakman et al., 2021)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															15	
(Li et al., 2021)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															14	
(Lamelongue et al., 2021)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															11	
(Van Wynsberghe, 2021)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															10	
(Bannour et al., 2021)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															10	
(Cao et al., 2021)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															7	
(Shaikh et al., 2021)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															7	
(Wu et al., 2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															22	
(Dodge et al., 2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															21	
(Kaack et al., 2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															20	
(Patterson et al., 2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															15	
(Georgiou et al., 2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															12	
(Ligozat et al., 2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															12	
(Robbins and Van Wynsberghe, 2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															10	
(Gupta et al., 2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															10	
(Zhou et al., 2023)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															30	
(Verdecchia et al., 2023)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															25	
(Menghani, 2023)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															22	
(Chen et al., 2023)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															18	
(Eilam et al., 2023)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															18	
(Luccioni et al., 2023)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															16	
(Tornede et al., 2023)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															13	
(Li et al., 2023)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															13	
(Bouza et al., 2023)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															13	
(Grun et al., 2023)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															6	
(Alzoubi and Mishra, 2024)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															29	
(Bolón-Canedo et al., 2024)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															23	
(Barbierato and Gatti, 2024)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															22	
(Longpre et al., 2024)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															19	
(Grun and Gronau, 2024)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															13	
(Wright et al., 2025)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																															20	
Σ			39	35	33	32	30	27	26	24	24	22	22	21	18	17	17	16	16	15	15	14	14	14	14	13	13	12	12	12	12	11	11	11	11	640	

Appendix G. LCA linkage

The following Table G.8 complements the aggregated phase-level view presented in the main manuscript by providing a more detailed subphase-level reading aid. It illustrates how the review-derived lifecycle categories may be analytically related to established LCA stages. This supplementary mapping is intended to increase transparency of the synthesis and does not imply a validated, exhaustive, or one-to-one correspondence between lifecycle activities and LCA phases.

Table G.8: Supplementary subphase-level analytical reading aid relating review-derived Green AI lifecycle categories to LCA stages.

Green AI lifecycle phase (Level-1)	Primary LCA linkage / typical contribution (Level-0)
1) Green hardware selection and infrastructure design	Primarily goal and scope, inventory, and interpretation; defines relevant hardware-system boundaries and provides the basis for embodied and operational impact assessment
1.1 Responsible material sourcing	Primarily inventory; supports impact assessment and interpretation through material origin, extraction, and supply-chain data
1.2 Low-impact manufacturing	Primarily inventory; supports impact assessment and interpretation through production-related energy, emissions, and material inputs
1.3 Green logistics	Primarily inventory; supports impact assessment and interpretation through transport-related flows and emissions
1.4 Energy-aware infrastructure	Goal and scope, inventory, impact assessment, and interpretation; defines infrastructure assumptions and links energy demand to environmental indicators
1.5 Incoming supply chain transparency	Goal and scope, inventory, and interpretation; supports system boundary definition, cut-off decisions, and completeness checks
2) Green AI development	Primarily goal and scope, inventory, impact assessment, and interpretation; links model design and development choices to measurable environmental consequences
2.1 Goal setting and business understanding	Primarily goal and scope; supports functional unit definition, system boundaries, baseline specification, and comparison logic
2.2 AI validation and non-AI alternative check	Primarily interpretation; supports comparative assessment and justification of the AI-based solution
2.3 Low-carbon data acquisition, collection, and preparation	Primarily inventory; supports impact assessment and interpretation through data-pipeline-related energy and infrastructure demands
2.4 Green AI design modeling	Primarily goal and scope and interpretation; supports design-space definition and trade-off framing
2.5 Transparent AI documentation	Primarily interpretation; supports traceability, reporting completeness, uncertainty communication, and reproducibility
2.6 AI system implementation and evaluation	Primarily inventory, impact assessment, and interpretation; links implementation choices to measured or estimated environmental effects
2.7 Efficient model training and testing	Primarily inventory and impact assessment; supports interpretation through compute-, energy-, and emissions-related trade-offs
2.8 Efficient hyperparameter tuning	Primarily inventory and interpretation; makes iterative optimization burdens and trade-offs analytically visible
2.9 Green model fine-tuning	Primarily inventory, impact assessment, and interpretation
2.10 Lifecycle-aware AI system evaluation	Primarily impact assessment and interpretation; consolidates environmental indicators and trade-off analysis across lifecycle stages
2.11 Continuous integration and delivery	Primarily inventory and interpretation; supports process-related efficiency and deployment-frequency considerations
2.12 Carbon-aware model compression	Primarily inventory, impact assessment, and interpretation; links model simplification to environmental and performance effects
2.13 Responsible Green AI	Primarily interpretation; supports broader evaluation of environmental implications, trade-offs, and reporting context
3) Low-footprint AI task realization	Primarily inventory, impact assessment, and interpretation; captures operational resource use and its environmental consequences during deployment and inference
3.1 Green deployment	Goal and scope, inventory, impact assessment, and interpretation; defines deployment context and links infrastructure choices to operational impacts
3.2 Energy-aware inference	Primarily inventory and impact assessment; supports interpretation through runtime energy and emissions trade-offs
3.3 Inference optimization	Primarily inventory and interpretation; supports trade-off analysis between latency, throughput, and environmental burden
3.4 Green AI operations	Primarily inventory, impact assessment, and interpretation; captures operational monitoring and resource-related environmental effects
3.5 Run-time, simulation, and regular AI sensitivity assessment	Primarily impact assessment and interpretation; supports sensitivity analysis and scenario-based evaluation
4) Circular AI maintenance and green administration	Primarily interpretation, supported by inventory and impact assessment updates during operation and maintenance
4.1 Proactive model monitoring and scorecard creation	Primarily inventory, impact assessment, and interpretation; updates performance-environment information during continued operation
4.2 Green compliance	Primarily interpretation; evaluates results against criteria, thresholds, and reporting requirements
4.3 Benchmarking with alternatives (AI and non-AI technologies)	Primarily interpretation; supports comparative evaluation of alternative technical solutions
4.4 Continuous improvements	Primarily interpretation; derives follow-up actions from observed environmental and performance outcomes
5) Green end-of-life and AI circularity	Primarily goal and scope, inventory, impact assessment, and interpretation; extends assessment to reuse, recovery, recycling, and disposal situations.
5.1 AI model reutilization	Primarily interpretation; supports lifecycle extension logic and avoided-burden reasoning where applicable
5.2 Resource recovery	Primarily inventory and impact assessment; supports interpretation through recovered-material and avoided-impact considerations
5.3 Circular recycling	Primarily inventory, impact assessment, and interpretation
5.4 AI model archivation	Primarily inventory and interpretation; captures storage-related resource use and retention decisions
5.5 AI model disposal	Primarily inventory, impact assessment, and interpretation
5.6 Outgoing supply chain transparency	Primarily inventory and interpretation; supports completeness, downstream boundary specification, and reporting transparency
Illustrative phase-level evaluation situations	Not an LCA phase; analytically informed by interpretation of inventory and impact assessment results
Act: adapt (external) / adjust (internal)	Not an LCA phase; represents follow-up improvement actions derived from interpretation

Appendix H. Transparency views

Appendix H.1. Illustrative notation-based transparency view of the review-derived lifecycle categories

The subsequent appendix figures provide more fine-grained visual decompositions of the five lifecycle phases.

Transparency-oriented reading aids. The appendix does not provide empirical validation of the review-derived lifecycle structure. Instead, it offers three transparency-oriented reading aids that help readers understand how the proposed analytical structuring is illustrated, how it is related to the LCA perspective adopted in the manuscript, and how selected published Green AI situations can be read in relation to it.

(1) Readability-oriented inspection of the illustrative visualization. The appendix visualization was reviewed only to ensure that the depicted progression and follow-up situations remain readable and notationally coherent within the chosen representation. This is a limited transparency check, not a validation of the lifecycle model itself.

(2) Constructed conceptual mapping as a reading aid. A Level-0 lifecycle overview and a detailed phase-to-stage matrix (Table G.8) were used as a transparency-oriented interpretive aid. Rather than assigning each lifecycle phase and subphase to a single LCA stage, the mapping shows how AI-related activities contribute across multiple LCA stages. In particular, activities generate inventory data (e.g., energy, material, and compute flows), contribute to impact assessment by transforming these flows into environmental indicators (e.g., CO₂e, water use, and material footprints), and inform the interpretation of these impacts in relation to performance and system boundaries. The mapping links AI-specific activities to established LCA stages. Impact assessment and interpretation are treated as methodological phases, not as procedural steps within the lifecycle. The mapping explicitly reflects core LCA concepts, including functional units (e.g., per inference or training run), system boundaries and cut-off criteria (e.g., inclusion of hardware lifecycle stages), allocation rules for shared infrastructure (e.g., data centers), and uncertainty in energy and carbon intensity estimates. In this way, AI-specific processes can be aligned with established environmental assessment practices while making often neglected areas, such as hardware provisioning and end-of-life recycling, more explicit.

Three limited observations follow from this mapping: (i) coverage: the review-derived lifecycle categories span upstream, operational, and down-

stream contexts in a continuous analytical structure; (ii) conceptual compatibility: the illustrative distinction can be read as informed by LCA-related interpretation, while remaining external to LCA methodology itself; (iii) transparency of correspondence: the multi-level view makes visible how the chosen lifecycle categories relate to established LCA concepts. These observations are intended as transparency-oriented aids for interpretation rather than as validation results.

(3) Literature-anchored illustrative plausibility check. The purpose of this step is not to validate a new process standard, but only to examine whether the review-derived lifecycle distinctions can be meaningfully illustrated using selected Green AI situations reported in the literature. The selected cases are used as externally documented reference points for interpretive comparison. They do not establish empirical generalizability or practical effectiveness of the model.

The cases were selected because they provide technically concrete and decision-relevant evidence for different lifecycle phases rather than discussing Green AI only at a high level. They were not intended to maximize empirical representativeness, but to test whether the proposed decision logic remains interpretable across distinct, externally documented Green AI situations. Taken together, they cover four core classes of Green AI decision situations. For each case, the following analytical questions were applied: (i) which lifecycle phase is affected, (ii) whether procedural completeness is satisfied, (iii) whether performance–environment conditions are satisfied, and (iv) which intervention logic follows under the review-derived model. This does not amount to statistical generalization. Its narrower purpose is to assess whether the proposed lifecycle logic remains interpretable and broadly plausible across heterogeneous published situations.

Lifecycle completeness and omitted upstream/downstream phases. Ligozat et al. (Ligozat et al., 2022) explicitly criticize environmental assessments of AI that focus narrowly on operational energy use and greenhouse gas emissions while neglecting production, transport, and end-of-life stages. To address this limitation, they structure the environmental assessment of AI solutions along the lifecycle stages of production, use, and end-of-life and argue that relevant impacts may otherwise remain systematically hidden. In the context of this review, this highlights the importance of lifecycle-complete assessment and the risk of underestimating environmental burdens when upstream or downstream phases are omitted. This is especially relevant for phases related to hardware provision and end-of-life.

Performance gains versus environmental burden. Strubell et al. (Strubell et al., 2019) show that improvements in NLP model performance can be associated with substantial increases in energy demand, carbon emissions, and development costs, especially when tuning and repeated experimentation are considered. Their estimates illustrate the scale of this effect: while training smaller models may remain comparatively moderate, reported emissions rise to 1,438 lbs CO₂e for BERT_{base} on GPU and up to 626,155 lbs CO₂e for neural architecture search. They further report that a case-study development process involved 4,789 jobs and a cumulative 9,998 GPU-days. These examples show that development activities can be completed while the resulting configuration remains environmentally burdensome. For this review, the relevant distinction is between process completion and environmental adequacy. The literature also discusses possible follow-up responses, including model simplification, compression, and more efficient retraining.

Carbon-aware operation through regional and temporal adaptation. Dodge et al. (Dodge et al., 2022) demonstrate that the carbon intensity of AI workloads in cloud environments varies significantly across regions and times of day and that emissions can be reduced through region selection, delayed start, or pause-and-resume strategies. For example, they report average carbon intensities of about 200 g CO₂/kWh in the most efficient region and 755 g CO₂/kWh in the least efficient region. For BERT training, they further show that choosing the execution region can shift emissions from about 7k grams to 26k grams CO₂, while time-of-day effects can change emissions by up to 8%. The intervention concerns the operational context (e.g., scheduling or location) rather than the model itself. This distinguishes *adapt* from model-internal adjustments.

Measurement and reporting as a condition of evaluability. Henderson et al. (Henderson et al., 2020) argue that systematic reporting of energy use, carbon intensity, hardware utilization, and regional electricity context is necessary for meaningful carbon and energy assessment in machine learning. They further emphasize that partial accounting can misrepresent actual impacts and that coarse compute proxies alone are insufficient for reliable environmental evaluation. In the context of this review, this implies that environmental assessment is only interpretable when the underlying measurement and reporting basis is explicitly defined. This case therefore highlights a basic condition of evaluability: environmentally relevant claims require traceable measurement assumptions, clearly specified system boundaries, and sufficiently complete reporting.

Taken together, the cross-case illustration supports three interpretive observations. First, the review-derived lifecycle logic can be related coherently to externally documented Green AI situations across heterogeneous lifecycle phases. Second, the cases suggest a useful analytical distinction between incomplete lifecycle coverage and environmentally unsatisfactory configurations within an otherwise covered lifecycle perspective. Omitted upstream or downstream elements indicate incomplete environmental assessment, whereas environmentally problematic hardware, energy, placement, or operational choices point to adverse impact patterns within the assessed configuration. Third, the distinction between *adapt* and *adjust* is not merely terminological, but corresponds to different intervention loci reported in the literature, namely changes in operational context versus changes in the AI artefact itself. Accordingly, the purpose of this cross-case assessment is not to establish formal empirical validation, but to illustrate how the review-derived lifecycle logic relates to published Green AI situations in an interpretable and transparent manner.

Appendix H.2. Green AI lifecycle—Detailed transparency views

The subsequent appendix figures provide more fine-grained visual decompositions of the five lifecycle phases. They are included solely as transparency-oriented reading aids for the review-derived category structure and should not be read as prescriptive process models, validated operational workflows, or evidence of notation-specific superiority.

Connected to the overview illustration of the lifecycle categories (high-level view), the detailed transparency views are organized as follows: Figure H.10 focuses on *Green hardware selection and infrastructure design*. *Green AI development* is presented in Figure H.11 and Figure H.12. Figure H.13 presents *Low-footprint AI task realization*. Figure H.14 presents *Circular AI maintenance and green administration*. Figure H.15 presents *Green end-of-life and AI circularity*.

Appendix H.2.1. Green AI lifecycle—Realize green hardware selection and infrastructure design

Figure H.10: Realize green hardware selection and infrastructure design.

Appendix H.2.2. Green AI lifecycle—Realize Green AI development part 1

Figure H.11: Realize Green AI development part 1.

Appendix H.2.3. Green AI lifecycle—Realize Green AI development part 2

Figure H.12: Realize Green AI development part 2.

Appendix H.2.4. Green AI lifecycle—Realize low-footprint AI task realization

Figure H.13: Realize low-footprint AI task realization.

Appendix H.2.5. Green AI lifecycle—Realize circular AI maintenance and green administration

Figure H.14: Realize circular AI maintenance and green administration.

Appendix H.2.6. Green AI lifecycle—Realize green end-of-life and AI circularity

Figure H.15: Realize green end-of-life and AI circularity.

Appendix I. Hardware

Appendix I.1. State-of-the-art of Green AI hardware

Energy consumption is a central determinant of overall Green AI performance, since training state-of-the-art models often requires megawatt-hours of electricity and sustained use of *Graphics Processing Units* (GPUs) / *Tensor Processing Units* (TPUs) with power draws exceeding hundreds of watts per device. Measurements at the rack and facility level consistently reveal that training can dominate operational footprints, while inference energy, accumulated over billions of queries, may exceed training in absolute terms. Quantifying these demands in J/inference or kWh/epoch is therefore indispensable for comparing hardware classes, optimizing workload placement, and assessing the long-term environmental trade-offs of architectural choices.

Edge computing leverages single-board computers (or rather embedded systems) to process data locally, reducing latency and transmission-related energy costs. These platforms combine compact form factors with modest power envelopes, making them suitable for distributed AI in industrial and IoT contexts. Typical examples discussed in the literature include Raspberry Pi boards, Banana Pi variants, and Arduino-based microcontrollers, each reflecting different workload and energy profiles. Illustrative measurements reported in prior studies indicate that a Raspberry Pi 3B with a 1.2 GHz ARM Cortex-A53 CPU consumes about 700 mW during inference, whereas an Arduino Uno R3 operates at roughly 175 mW (Albreem et al., 2021). Such differences highlight a clear trade-off between computational capability and energy efficiency: while Raspberry Pi devices can support lightweight neural networks or even quantized CNNs, microcontrollers like Arduino excel in ultra-low-power monitoring or control tasks. Recent studies discuss specialized edge accelerators (e.g., Intel Movidius NCS, NVIDIA Jetson Nano/Xavier) as illustrative examples that expand the design space, offering GPU-class inference performance at only a few watts (Zhu et al., 2022).

The energy footprint of AI systems is determined not only by GPUs but also by orchestration CPUs, multi-terabyte RAM pools, and high-bandwidth storage arrays that sustain data pipelines (Bannour et al., 2021). Empirical profiling shows that *preprocessing* and *feature extraction* can consume up to 30% of node-level energy, largely invisible in GPU-centric accounts. Access to accelerators is further limited by high acquisition cost and scarce scheduling capacity, creating structural disparities between hyperscale providers and

academic clusters. Consequently, *hybrid CPU–GPU infrastructures* dominate HPC deployments, with CPUs managing I/O, checkpointing, and inter-node communication, while GPUs handle matrix-heavy kernels (Menghani, 2023). Coordinated optimization across compute, memory, and storage tiers is therefore essential, since isolated GPU efficiency gains cannot fully mitigate system-level energy demand.

In addition to GPUs, task-specific accelerators such as Google’s TPUs and modern NPUs are frequently discussed in the literature as relevant options for ML computation. Their matrix-oriented systolic arrays can support high degrees of parallelism, drastically improving throughput and energy efficiency in both training and inference phases relative to general-purpose GPUs (Yokoyama et al., 2023). The power efficiency of TPUs and NPUs arises from their domain-specific design for matrix multiplications and low-precision arithmetic, supporting significantly higher throughput-per-watt than general-purpose GPUs. When deployed at hyperscale in data centers, TPU/NPU pods have been reported to reduce training energy by 2–5× in specific settings for transformer-class models, translating into measurable cuts in CO₂e emissions per run (Jouppi et al., 2023). Efficiency gains matter most for transformer-based large language models and recommendation pipelines, where matrix-multiplication kernels (GEMM) dominate both training and inference energy use.

Low-power accelerators like NVIDIA’s Jetson modules combine ARM cores and CUDA GPUs on compact SoCs, supporting computer vision inference at 30–50 TOPS while staying under 30 W. Intel’s Myriad VPU line uses fixed-function units and on-chip caches to minimize DRAM access, cutting the energy footprint of frame-level video analytics by an order of magnitude. For hyperscale deployments, Cloud TPUs offer 100+ TFLOPS per board with demonstrably higher FLOPS-per-watt ratios than flagship GPUs, providing measurable carbon savings in large-scale training runs. Yet, modern high-end GPUs such as the H100 or RTX A6000 are often used in the literature to illustrate trade-offs: their unprecedented throughput requires extensive cooling and interconnect energy, escalating the total footprint of ML infrastructure in research labs and data centers.

The extreme throughput of accelerators is inseparable from high-energy requirements for cooling, connections, and storage, pushing training jobs for frontier models into multi-megawatt territory and creating quantifiable Green AI risks for AI data centers. The hardware classification Table I.9 therefore serves as an illustrative analytical baseline to compare CPUs, GPUs, TPUs,

NPUs, and edge devices along energy, carbon, and lifecycle attributes, highlighting heterogeneity that directly affects footprint reporting. It summarizes representative configurations discussed in prior studies, spanning CPUs, GPUs, and specialized AI accelerators (e.g., TPUs). Beyond technical specifications (cores, memory, accelerator details, thermal design power), the Table I.9 also aligns configurations with common deployment classes (local CPS level, local cloud, public cloud) to highlight ecosystem diversity rather than prescribe concrete devices.

The Table I.9 provides an illustrative overview of hardware configurations discussed in the Green AI literature. It includes conventional CPUs and GPUs as well as domain-specific accelerators such as TPUs or NPUs. Beyond technical specifications (core count, memory bandwidth, GPU FLOPS, interconnect bandwidth), the classification considers hardware form factor (desktop workstation, embedded single-board computer, rack-scale accelerator), instruction-set architecture (x86, ARM, RISC-V), and deployment context (edge-level CPS nodes, private enterprise clusters, hyperscale cloud regions). This differentiation enables mapping diverse hardware choices directly to their energy profiles and ecological implications across all lifecycle stages.

The classification highlights trade-offs between energy efficiency, compute power, and infrastructure dependency by mapping hardware classes to typical deployment contexts. It thus underlines how different device types, from CPUs to accelerators, map to distinct lifecycle and deployment contexts. Further, it becomes clear that ARM-based single-board computers (e.g., Raspberry Pi, NVIDIA Jetson) are suited for low-power, local CPS scenarios, whereas x86-based servers with accelerators (e.g., V100/H100-class GPUs) are used in local or public cloud settings for performance-intensive workloads. This class-based view emphasizes trade-offs between energy efficiency, compute capacity, and infrastructure coupling, without constituting device-level recommendations.

The Table I.9 reflects an emerging trend: recent studies compare hardware platforms regarding their energy measurement capabilities (Rojahn and Grum, 2025). Results vary with workload type (e.g., training versus inference), deployment context (edge, enterprise, cloud), and infrastructure conditions such as cooling, energy mix, and interconnects. Despite this limitation, it provides a structured baseline for comparing hardware options and identifying configurations with lower embodied and operational impacts, thereby informing more sustainable AI system design. Since environmental performance depends on regional and infrastructural context, the next section ex-

tends hardware profiling to whole-system monitoring, including storage arrays, interconnect traffic, and idle baseloads. Context-specific variables—grid mix dynamics, cooling technologies, and workload duty cycles—should be reported where available together with measurement data. This prevents device-level bias and supports reproducibility across sites with different infrastructures or energy mixes.

Analytical comparison dimensions. Across the reviewed literature, hardware comparison commonly varies along four dimensions: (i) technical suitability for the workload, (ii) platform-level energy efficiency, (iii) contextual carbon intensity of electricity, and (iv) lifecycle impacts such as embodied emissions over service life and utilization. These dimensions help explain why hardware results differ across studies and why device-level comparisons remain difficult without explicit contextual disclosure. (Anthony et al., 2020; Henderson et al., 2020).

Thus, the following six steps can be distinguished in the literature: (1) Profile the workload (compute/memory/I/O characteristics, Service Level Agreements, SLAs, duty cycles). (2) Enumerate candidate *classes* (SBC/edge accelerators, workstations, on-premises servers, public cloud accelerators). (3) Assess energy under representative benchmark runs; combine device telemetry with whole-system measurements (e.g., smart plugs, rack Power Distribution Units, PDUs) to capture additional non-accelerator loads (Anthony et al., 2020). (4) Bind context explicitly: region(s), Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), water cooling characteristics, and scheduling windows to reflect spatial and temporal variation in grid carbon intensity (Henderson et al., 2020). (5) Include embodied lifecycle impacts of acquisition and replacement cycles (Li et al., 2023). (6) Report all methodological assumptions (location, temporal granularity, infrastructure characteristics, measurement method) in a standardized form to ensure reproducibility and cross-study comparability (Henderson et al., 2020).

Appendix I.2. Overview of Green AI hardware

Table I.9 provides an illustrative overview of hardware instances discussed in the reviewed Green AI literature. The table is intended as a non-prescriptive transparency aid that documents the heterogeneity of reported hardware contexts across local CPS, local cloud, and public cloud settings rather than prescribing preferred devices or configurations.

Table I.9: Illustrative overview of hardware instances discussed in the Green AI literature (non-prescriptive).

Source	Core Type	CPU	Accel. detail	RAM	GPU	GPU RAM	GPU Cores	Hardware type	Hardware architecture	Illustrative deployment class
(Altheim et al., 2021)	CPU	Arduino Uno R3	1 C	-	-	-	-	Single-board comp. (SBC)	AVR	Local CPS
(Altheim et al., 2021)	CPU	Arduino Mega 2560	4 C	-	-	-	-	Single-board computer	AVR	Local CPS
(Altheim et al., 2021)	CPU	Banan Pi	4 C	1 GB	-	-	-	Single-board computer	ARM	Local CPS
(Altheim et al., 2021)	CPU	Raspberry Pi 3B	4 C	1 GB	-	-	-	Single-board computer	ARM	Local CPS
(Hamour et al., 2021)	CPU	Raspberry Pi 3B	4 C	1 GB	-	-	-	Single-board computer	ARM	Local CPS
(Zhu et al., 2022)	GPU	Jetson Xavier NX	6 C	8 GB	-	16 GB	5120	AI Accelerator	x86	Local CPS
(Zhu et al., 2022)	Both	Jetson Xavier NX	6 C	8 GB	-	16 GB	5120	SBC / AI Accelerator	ARM	Local CPS
(Yokeyama et al., 2023)	Both	Denver 2.2 GHz	18 C	24 GB	Pascal @ 1300 MHz	-	768	AI Accelerator	ARM	Local CPS
(Yokeyama et al., 2023)	Both	ARM v8.2 64-bit	8 C	32 GB	NVIDIA Volta	-	512	Server GPU / AI Accel.	ARM	Local CPS
(Yokeyama et al., 2023)	CPU	i7 8700 @ 3.2 GHz	6 C	64 GB	-	-	54	Desktop GPU	x86	Local CPS
(Yokeyama et al., 2023)	Both	i7 8700 @ 3.2 GHz	6 C	64 GB	-	11 GB	128	Desktop CPU and GPU	x86	Local CPS
(Yokeyama et al., 2023)	Both	NVIDIA Jetson Nano	4 C	4 GB	RTX 2080 Ti, 1546 MHz	-	256	AI Accelerator	ARM	Local CPS
(Yokeyama et al., 2023)	Both	NVIDIA Jetson TX2	6 C	8 GB	128-Core Maxwell GPU	-	-	AI Accelerator	ARM	Local CPS
(Yokeyama et al., 2023)	CPU	Raspberry Pi 4	4 C	1 GB	-	-	-	Single-board computer	ARM	Local CPS
(Yokeyama et al., 2023)	GPU	-	-	-	RTX 4000 SFF	20 GB	6144	Desktop GPU	x86	Local CPS
(Sprind, 2024)	GPU	-	-	-	RTX A6000	48 GB	10752	Workstation GPU	x86	Local cloud
(Sprind, 2024)	CPU	EPYC 7R13	64 C	-	-	-	-	Server CPU	x86	Local cloud
(Sprind, 2024)	CPU	Intel Xeon 8175	28 C	-	-	-	-	Server CPU	x86	Local cloud
(Yokeyama et al., 2023)	Both	NVIDIA Jetson AGX Xavier	8 C	32 GB	-	128 GB	3584	AI Accelerator	ARM	Local cloud
(Yokeyama et al., 2023)	Both	Jetson Nano	-	-	512-Core Volta GPU	128 GB	-	Server GPU / AI Accel.	ARM	Local cloud
(Xu et al., 2023)	GPU	-	-	-	Tesla P100-PCIE-16GB	16 GB	3584	AI Accelerator	x86	Local cloud
(Xu et al., 2023)	Both	E5-2698 v4, 2.2 GHz	20 C	-	Tesla P100-PCIE-16GB	32 GB	5120	AI Accelerator	x86	Local cloud
(Qu et al., 2023)	Both	Gold 6152, 2.1 GHz	22 C	-	Tesla V100-SXM2-32GB	32 GB	5120	Server GPU / AI Accel. and CPU	x86	Local cloud
(Sprind, 2024)	GPU	-	-	-	Tesla V100 PCIe-32 GB	48 GB	18176	Server GPU / AI Accel.	x86	Local cloud
(Sprind, 2024)	AI TP.	-	-	-	L40S	128 GB	-	AI Accelerator	x86	Public cloud
(Sprind, 2024)	GPU	-	-	-	Habana Gaudi	94 GB	14502	Server GPU / AI Accel.	x86	Public cloud
(Sprind, 2024)	GPU	-	-	-	NVIDIA H100	94 GB	14502	Server GPU / AI Accel.	x86	Public cloud

Appendix I.3. Conceptual hardware deployment classes

Building on the illustrative device-level overview in Table I.9, Table I.10 abstracts the reported configurations into recurring deployment classes. The table is non-prescriptive and serves to distinguish hardware contexts relevant for Green AI assessment across local CPS, local cloud, and public cloud settings.

Table I.10: Conceptual hardware deployment classes for Green AI across edge, local, and cloud infrastructures. The table abstracts from device-level examples documented in Table I.9.

Deployment Level	Hardware Class	Typical Characteristics	Examples (abstracted)
Local-CPS-Level (Edge)	Low-power embedded devices	Very low-power consumption, limited compute, often CPU-only	Microcontrollers, simple IoT devices
	Single-board computers	Low-power, limited memory, no, or minimal GPU	SBC platforms (e.g., Raspberry Pi class)
	Embedded AI accelerators	Low to moderate power, integrated GPU/AI accelerator	Edge AI modules (e.g., Jetson class)
	Personal devices	Moderate compute, integrated CPU/GPU	Smartphones, laptops
Local-Cloud-Level	Workstations	High compute capacity, GPU-enabled	Single-node GPU systems
	On-premises servers	High compute and memory, multi-GPU systems	Enterprise servers
Public-Cloud-Level	Cloud compute instances	Highly scalable, virtualized compute resources	Cloud-based GPU/CPU instances
	Large-scale accelerator clusters	Very high compute density, distributed systems	Multi-GPU/TPU clusters

Appendix J. Measurement

Appendix J.1. State-of-the-art of measuring Green AI

The review reveals that existing measurement approaches form a heterogeneous spectrum ranging from lightweight software estimators to infrastructure-grade metering. As summarized in Table J.11, *Python-based libraries* such as *CodeCarbon*, *Experiment Impact Tracker*, or *Carbontracker* integrate directly into machine learning workflows, but rely on static emission factors and Thermal Design Power (TDP) assumptions. While these tools offer portability and low integration overhead, empirical studies show deviations of up to 40–60% when workloads combine GPU-intensive training with I/O-heavy preprocessing or distributed inference across heterogeneous regions (Henderson et al., 2020; Acun et al., 2023). *Cloud-provider dashboards* (e.g., Google or Microsoft) represent a second class of indirect tools, reporting energy and carbon footprints at service and region level. Their coverage is enriched by provider-side infrastructure data, yet constrained by proprietary scope and limited transparency regarding water withdrawals, allocation rules, and embodied impacts (Microsoft, 2020; Google LLC, 2021). In contrast to estimation approaches, *direct metering methods* provide empirical ground truth across multiple abstraction layers. External meters—such as rack-mounted PDUs or smart plugs—capture total-system energy, including conversion and cooling losses, ensuring robust system-level accuracy but limited component attribution (Ligozat et al., 2022). Their independence from specific architectures (Operating system, hardware, or software) enables consistent monitoring of heterogeneous distributed environments. Integrated *performance monitoring counters* (PMCs) and on-board sensors allow fine-grained attribution at millisecond resolution but vary widely across chip types and require privileged access or cross-validation. *Hybrid frameworks* (e.g., IrEne (Cao et al., 2021)) combine model-based estimates with measured data. These approaches indicate that measurement remains fragmented across system layers and lacks a unified cross-layer integration.

Python packages. Tools such as *CodeCarbon* (CodeCarbon, 2021), *Experiment Impact Tracker* (Henderson et al., 2020), and *Carbontracker* (Anthony et al., 2020) are lightweight Python libraries that hook into ML training loops, recording runtime duration, hardware type, and regional grid mix to estimate energy use and associated CO₂ emissions.

Their strength lies in portability and low overhead, but methodology is inherently indirect. Typically, these packages: (i) obtain hardware utiliza-

tion (CPU/GPU time, memory) via existing ML frameworks or OS counters, (ii) map this utilization to power draw using static lookup tables or manufacturer-reported TDP values, and (iii) multiply energy consumption with average grid carbon intensities drawn from open datasets (e.g., IEA).

This approach rests on critical assumptions: constant efficiency factors, limited accuracy of manufacturer TDP ratings, and neglect of system-level overhead (e.g., cooling, conversion losses). Recent studies show such estimates can deviate significantly (up to 40–60%) from direct power measurements, especially for heterogeneous or dynamic workloads (Patterson et al., 2021; Acun et al., 2023). Their reliability therefore depends strongly on workload type and local calibration.

Online tools. Accessible interfaces such as *EnergyVis* (Shaikh et al., 2021) and the *ML Emissions Calculator* (Lacoste et al., 2019) target awareness rather than precise profiling. They typically accept model parameters (epochs, dataset size, hardware type) and return coarse-grained estimates using efficiency constants. Their value lies in communication and pedagogy, but they lack the fidelity required for system-level optimization or study-grade reporting.

Corporate dashboards. Cloud-native dashboards such as Google’s Carbon Footprint (Google LLC, 2021) or Microsoft’s Emissions Impact Dashboard (Microsoft, 2020) provide richer data than open-source libraries, as they access data center-level telemetry (cooling, Power Usage Effectiveness, PUE; and localized grid mix). These dashboards report aggregated, auditable emissions, often broken down by region and service class. However, they remain proprietary: transparency into methods is limited, external validation is difficult, and applicability is restricted to workloads inside the provider’s ecosystem. They cannot be generalized to hybrid or on-premises infrastructures, limiting scientific utility for reproducible research (Ligozat et al., 2022).

Hardware-based measurement. A persistent limitation of many AI-specific tools is their lack of integration with direct hardware instrumentation, such as rack-level power meters, smart plugs (e.g., Shelly), or performance monitoring counters (PMCs) providing ground-truth energy data for CPUs and GPUs. Yet in Green IT and HPC research, external energy meters and integrated PMCs have long been standard. External meters (e.g., rack PDUs, smart plugs) capture full-system consumption, including overhead, but lack component attribution. Integrated PMCs (used in benchmarks such as *Perun* and the *ML Energy Benchmark* (Tornede et al., 2023)) enable fine-grained,

per-component analysis with minimal latency, but often require privileged access and careful calibration. Both approaches offer higher accuracy than indirect methods, but remain underutilized in AI-specific tooling.

Beyond energy: water and other resources. Attempts to extend Green AI monitoring to water usage remain experimental. Li et al. (Li et al., 2023) propose indirect estimation of water consumption based on regional cooling requirements and data center energy-water conversion factors. However, these models rely on coarse averages and lack validation against direct measurements. As water becomes a critical constraint in data center siting (Zhou et al., 2023), the absence of robust, tool-supported methodologies is a major research gap.

Critical appraisal. Overall, existing tools either provide accessible but coarse-grained estimates (Python packages, online tools) or detailed yet proprietary dashboards (corporate solutions). High-precision methods from Green IT (external meters, PMCs) are known but rarely integrated into AI libraries. This fragmentation hampers comparability and slows progress toward standardized benchmarks. The state of the art reflects a methodological tension: *indirect but accessible* versus *direct but fragmented*. Bridging these approaches (e.g., hybrid architectures combining software hooks with calibrated hardware telemetry) represents a pressing research frontier.

Synthesis of tool coverage. Table J.11 further highlights the fragmented nature of the current measurement landscape. Out of 16 tools identified, Python packages dominate in terms of adoption (8/16), but offer only partial coverage of system boundaries. Corporate dashboards and online tools are fewer (3 and 3, respectively), yet they concentrate unique access to data center telemetry and pedagogical communication functions. In contrast, only a small subset integrates hardware-level telemetry or embodied-impact extensions, despite their recognized importance in Green IT research (Patterson et al., 2021; Acun et al., 2023; Tornede et al., 2023). The quantitative distribution therefore confirms the qualitative tension identified above: a trade-off between easily applicable estimator-based approaches and more accurate but resource-intensive direct measurement.

Implications for standardization. The imbalance revealed by the tool census suggests that methodological progress in Green AI measurement is currently skewed toward software-level convenience at the expense of physical accuracy. This imbalance has two consequences: first, the comparability across studies is undermined by inconsistent boundaries (device-only versus whole-system, average versus time-varying carbon intensity). However, since

AI infrastructures can contain distributed and heterogeneous computing systems, a system-wide measurement approach is essential. Second, important Green AI dimensions, such as water or material footprints, remain critically underrepresented (Li et al., 2023; Zhou et al., 2023). Bridging this gap requires hybrid approaches that combine lightweight integration with calibrated hardware telemetry, further improved by open protocols for transparently reporting assumptions (location, PUE, temporal granularity). Such a synthesis would enable reproducible, cross-platform benchmarking by mandating calibration of estimator outputs against hardware meters and harmonizing emission-factor provenance, thereby aligning AI-specific tools with the validated measurement protocols long established in HPC and Green IT research.

Appendix J.2. Summary of Green AI measurement tools

Table J.11 summarizes the Green AI measurement tools identified in the reviewed literature and shows in which studies they are reported. The heatmap is included as a transparency-oriented overview of tool coverage across Python packages, online tools, dashboards, cloud-related tools, and water-oriented tools, rather than as a prescriptive evaluation of tool quality.

Table J.11: Summary of Green AI measurement tools (fulfilled: ✓; not fulfilled: empty) as heatmap. The heatmap ranges from blue-white-red.

Unit of Analysis / Source	Python Packages						Online Tools			Dashboards		Cloud	Water			
	OECD AI (OECD, 2023)	Eco2AI (Budenny et al., 2022)	Efne (Cao et al., 2021)	CodeCarbon/MILCO ₂ (CodeCarbon, 2021)	Carbon Tracker (Anthony et al., 2020)	Experiment Impact Tracker (Henderson et al., 2020)	CUMULATOR (Trébaol, 2020)	Energy Usage (Lottick et al., 2019)	Green Algorithms (Lannelongue et al., 2021)	ML Emissions Calculator (Lacoste et al., 2019)	EnergyVis (Shaikh et al., 2021)	Carbon Footprint Tool (AWS, 2022)	Carbon Footprint (Google LLC, 2021)	Emissions Impact Dashboard (Microsoft, 2020)	Cloud Carbon Footprint (Thoughtworks, 2021)	Water Estimation Tool (Li et al., 2023)
(Lottick et al., 2019)							✓		✓							1
(Lacoste et al., 2019)								✓	✓							1
(Anthony et al., 2020)								✓	✓							3
(Trébaol, 2020)							✓		✓							3
(Henderson et al., 2020)							✓		✓							1
(Bannour et al., 2021)							✓		✓							7
(Patterson et al., 2021)							✓		✓							4
(Shaikh et al., 2021)							✓		✓							3
(Van Wynsberghe, 2021)							✓		✓							2
(Cao et al., 2021)							✓		✓							1
(Parcollet and Ravanello, 2021)							✓		✓							1
(Lannelongue et al., 2021)							✓		✓							1
(Ligezat et al., 2022)							✓		✓							5
(Budenny et al., 2022)							✓		✓							6
(Dodge et al., 2022)							✓		✓							2
(Patterson et al., 2022)							✓		✓							1
(Bouza et al., 2023)							✓		✓							8
(Tormede et al., 2023)							✓		✓							6
(Yokoyama et al., 2023)							✓		✓							5
(Zhou et al., 2023)							✓		✓							4
(Martínez-Fernández et al., 2023)							✓		✓							4
(Luccioni et al., 2023)							✓		✓							3
(Li et al., 2023)							✓		✓							2
(Verdecchia et al., 2023)							✓		✓							1
(Xu et al., 2023)							✓		✓							1
(Alzoubi and Mishra, 2024)							✓		✓							8
(Longpre et al., 2024)							✓		✓							8
(Bolíon-Cañedo et al., 2024)							✓		✓							3
Total per Tool	1	3	2	15	18	14	3	3	13	14	3	2	2	1	1	98

Appendix J.3. Measurement methods and reporting

Table J.12 systematizes the reviewed approaches along two dimensions: *indirect versus direct measurement* and *system- versus component-level granularity*.

Table J.12: Comparison of measurement methods for Green AI assessment.

Method	Type	Granularity	Strengths	Limitations
Software-based estimators (CodeCarbon, Experiment Impact Tracker)	Indirect (model-based)	System-level (approx.)	Easy integration; portable; minimal setup	Relies on emission factors; low accuracy under heterogeneous loads (Henderson et al., 2020; CodeCarbon, 2021)
Cloud dashboards (e.g., Google or Microsoft)	Indirect (provider-reported)	Data center-/region-level	Access to provider infrastructure data; automated aggregation	Proprietary scope; limited transparency; inapplicable beyond providers (Microsoft, 2020; Google LLC, 2021)
External meters (smart plugs, rack PDUs)	Direct metered data	Device-/rack-level	Captures device- or rack-level power draw within the specified measurement boundary.	Cannot isolate components; susceptible to conversion inefficiencies
Integrated sensors (PMCs, motherboard sensors)	Direct (component-level)	CPU/GPU, memory, accelerator	High temporal resolution; fine-grained attribution	Requires technical expertise; inconsistent availability across hardware (Tornede et al., 2023)
Hybrid approaches (software and external/internal meters)	Combined	Multi-tier (system and component)	Balances portability and precision; enables method calibration.	Rarely standardized; higher setup effort; limited tool support (Cao et al., 2021; Verdecchia et al., 2023)

Appendix J.4. Green AI measurement approaches

Figure J.16 summarizes the methodological space along the two axes of measurement type and granularity.

While Figure J.16 provides structural clarity, its practical implications are substantial. *Indirect system-level estimators* (e.g., *CodeCarbon*, *Experiment Impact Tracker*) can deviate markedly from metered values under heterogeneous workloads (Henderson et al., 2020; Acun et al., 2023). These deviations arise because estimator-based approaches typically abstract from parts of whole-system overhead, such as cooling, conversion losses, or data-movement effects, unless such factors are explicitly modeled or calibrated. Without calibration against measured data, reported footprints therefore remain sensitive to workload composition and infrastructure context.

Figure J.16: Conceptual mapping of Green AI measurement along two axes: (indirect versus direct) and (system- versus component-level granularity). Software packages (e.g., *CodeCarbon*, *Carbontracker*) rely on emission factors and grid averages (Anthony et al., 2020; Henderson et al., 2020). Cloud dashboards (e.g., Google or Microsoft) report region- and service-specific data with limited transparency (Microsoft, 2020; Google LLC, 2021). External meters (e.g., smart plugs, rack PDUs) capture device- or rack-level power within the specified measurement boundary but provide limited component attribution. Integrated sensors (PMCs, benchmarks like *Perun*, *ML Energy Benchmark*) provide fine-grained data but require calibration (Tornede et al., 2023). Hybrid approaches combine software with calibrated hardware telemetry, balancing portability and precision (Cao et al., 2021; Verdecchia et al., 2023).

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